

**D1.3 Modeling the impact of three
FLW reducing policy pathways at the
meso and macro level**

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PART I

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1: Glossary of terms and acronyms used.

Acronym / Term	Description
CES	Constant Elasticity of Substitution
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FAH	Food at home
FAFH	Food away from home
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
HRI	Hotels, restaurants and institutions
MAGNET	Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool
P1	Policy pathway 1
P2	Policy pathway 2
P3	Policy pathway 3
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
THS	Transport, handling and storage
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Working package

Executive summary

This deliverable consists of two parts. The first part presents the results of a partial equilibrium supply chain model documented in D1.2 of this project. The second part presents the results of a computable general equilibrium model Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool (MAGNET). The partial equilibrium model provides more details at the level of the supply chain and focuses on one commodity at a time. The MAGNET model is more aggregated but offers a broader geographical coverage and considers several food items/commodities at the same time. The MAGNET model treats all food waste as edible, whereas the partial equilibrium model distinguishes between edible and inedible food waste. The different structures and initial behavioural parameters of both models make a direct comparison of their results challenging. Hence, the results should be seen as complementary rather than directly comparable.

The first part of the deliverable shows the simulation results of three FLW-reducing policy pathways developed in deliverable 8.1. The take-home messages of this analysis include: (1) A high tax on the FLW disposal cost is required to approach the mandatory targets of the three policy pathways. Therefore, solely taxing FLW disposal is not a feasible approach and additional interventions (e.g., those investigated in the ZeroW SILLs) are required; (2) The share of inedible FLW in total FLW plays an important role in reducing total FLW; (3) Sectors that do not experience any increase in disposal costs through taxes, increase their FLW rate when other sectors are targeted by the tax; (4) The decrease in the consumption of food at home is an important outcome to consider for the development of FLW reduction targets.

The second part of the deliverable finds that regardless of the specific instrument used to reduce FLW, several unintended spillover effects emerge from reduction policies, potentially offsetting the anticipated benefits of FLW interventions. First, economic spillovers into food production increase land demand, use, and prices in 2030 and 2050. Second, positive social spillovers are found in a moderate average increase in wages for workers in agriculture. Lastly, environmental spillovers are found in the increased emissions from non-food sectors and agricultural sectors respectively driven by a higher non-food demand and use of chemical fertilisers. Tackling spillover effects is crucial for devising policy measures that are capable of minimising arising unintended negative effects. Taxes on FLW generation prove to be more effective in containing spillovers compared to stand-alone voluntary reductions.

1. Introduction

1.1. ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance.

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2: ZeroW approach.

To reach its goals, ZeroW is divided into 11 Work Packages (WPs) with different goals, tasks and deliverables. This deliverable (1.3) is part of WP1 'Modelling Food Loss and Waste (FLW) economics from Farm to Fork (F2F)' and builds further upon the earlier work that was done within WP1 (see figure 3 for an overview of WP1). Deliverable 1.1 developed a conceptual framework on FLW along the supply chain. This conceptual framework determined the boundaries of the generic food supply chain and served as a foundation for the development of the economic FLW model of deliverable 1.2. Deliverable 1.2 described the behavioural assumptions for food supply chain (FSC) actors, that is, how they maximise their profit or utility, how they can reduce their FLW generation and how the separate stages of the supply chain are linked. This deliverable (1.3) applies the model of D1.2 to four commodities - chicken, fruit, bread, and milk - that will represent different food groups with their own characteristics such as prices and the degree of perishability.

Figure 3: WP1 tasks, deliverables, objectives.

The model will be used to simulate several policies that aim to reduce FLW. These policies have been designed by WP8 'Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW'. In their first deliverable (D8.1), WP8 has described three policy pathways with distinct FLW reduction targets for FSC actors in 2030 and 2050. The simulations show the economic effects of the policies on the FSC.

1.2. Mapping ZeroW outputs

The purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document. Table 2 provides an overview.

Table 2: Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.3 Empirical results	<i>Provides results of modelling FLW interventions.</i>	5	<i>Chapter 5 shows and explains the outcomes of the policy simulations for four commodities.</i>
TASKS			
T1.3 Modelling the impact of FLW interventions at the meso level	<i>In this Task, data from the official national and EU statistics as well as SILLs will be used to calibrate the model developed in T1.2 for four selected food sectors. In calibrating the model, we will consult with SILLs to finetune the outcomes of the model. The objective of this task is to provide quantitative estimates of the economic effects (change in prices, quantities, food loss and waste, and welfare) of private and public interventions in the food supply chain. The interventions to be tested will be provided in the form of</i>	2, 3, 4 and 5	<i>Chapter 2 summarizes the policy pathways of D8.1. Chapter 3 provides an overview of the modelled food supply chain based on D1.2. Chapter 4 gives an outline of the most important data of the four simulated commodities. Chapter 5 displays and explains the results of the simulations and shows the cascading effect along the supply chain.</i>

	<p><i>alternative near-zero pathways from T8.1. We will study the cascading effect of these interventions at a particular stage of the supply chain on the upstream and downstream actors. The results of this empirical task will be directly relevant to T8.2 & T8.3 as they will form a quantitative basis for policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW</i></p>		
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is structured as follows. Chapter 2 explains how FLW can be reduced along the supply chain, and which policy targets are proposed in deliverable 8.1. Chapter 3 explains the most relevant details of the supply chain model. Chapter 4 gives a brief overview of the input data used for the supply chain models. Chapter 5 describes the results of the simulations, and chapter 6 concludes this deliverable and discusses the results. Annex I shows the functional forms that operationalise the model from deliverable 1.2; Annex II explains how the model is calibrated; Annex III provides an overview of all the input data used for this deliverable, and Annex IV shows the results of voluntary reduction targets.

2. Reducing food loss and waste in the supply chain

The FSC is complex, with linkages across stages. A shock in one stage of the supply chain will inevitably affect other stages. These interlinkages are also exhibited when changes in FLW are evaluated. FLW generated in one stage of the supply chain affects the quantity produced and its price at other stages. De Gorter et al. (2021) showed how these interlinkages work and concluded that elasticities and initial rates of FLW at each stage are important. These characteristics of a food product determine whether cascading effects reinforce FLW-reducing policies or (partially) offset the achieved reduction at this stage. The economic effects of FLW-reducing policies are simulated for this deliverable based on an adapted version of the model of de Gorter et al. (2021). We explained the adaptations in deliverable 1.2 and the policies that will be simulated are based on deliverable 8.1.

The three policy pathways developed for deliverable 8.1 serve as a basis for the policy objectives in the simulations of this deliverable. These policy pathways set total (edible and inedible) FLW reduction goals for different stages of the supply chain by 2030. The policy pathways differ from each other in terms of ambition to reduce FLW per stage of the supply chain (excluding pre-harvest losses), and whether these goals are mandatory (i.e., legally binding) or voluntary (i.e., not legally binding).

The first policy pathway only sets FLW reduction goals for 2032 (D'haese et al., 2023). The reduction goals are listed in Table 3. There are no FLW reduction goals for primary production in this policy pathway. Processing and manufacturing will have to reduce the weight of FLW they generate by 10%. On top of the mandatory goal, they receive a voluntary goal of 25% of their baseline FLW generation. The objectives for retail and consumption are higher. These sectors receive a mandatory goal to reduce their FLW by 30% and a voluntary goal of 50% with respect to the

baseline year. The first policy pathway should be achieved through a market-driven policy approach combined with a high degree of investment in innovation and research.

Table 3: FLW reduction targets in policy pathway 1 (D'haese et al., 2023).

Food waste reduction target on	Mandatory FW reduction target in 2032	Voluntary FW reduction target in 2032
Primary production	n/a	n/a
Processing and manufacturing	10% (absolute amounts in mass units)	25% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail	30% (per capita)	50% (per capita)
Consumption	30% (per capita)	50% (per capita)

The second policy pathway sets the most ambitious FLW reduction targets for the FSC (Table 4). This policy pathway does not distinguish between different stages of the food supply chain; each stage will have to reduce the mass of FLW by the same percentage. Pre-harvest losses are, however, not included in this policy pathway. The mandatory FLW reduction goal for each stage of the supply chain is 50% in 2030. The role of voluntary reduction targets is limited in this policy pathway. Voluntary commitments can be used to highlight the progress of frontrunners in reducing FLW, but because there is no specific goal, we will not simulate them.

Table 4: FLW reduction targets in policy pathway 2 (D'haese et al., 2023).

Food waste reduction target on	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target
Primary production	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)	For higher target levels
Processing and manufacturing	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)	For higher target levels
Retail & Consumption	50% (per capita)	For higher target levels

Note: The voluntary higher target level reductions are undetermined. The supply chain actors can determine their own, more ambitious FLW reduction goals.

Unlike policy pathway 1 (P1) and 2 (P2), policy pathway 3 (P3) (Table 5) moves away from mandatory targets. The only mandatory target that exists in this pathway is a 15% reduction per capita for retail and consumption by 2030. P3 focusses more on voluntary agreements to reduce FLW. Primary production receives a voluntary reduction goal of 10%, while processing and manufacturing, and retail and consumption both receive a voluntary goal of 50% in 2030.

Table 5: FLW reduction targets in policy pathway 3 (D'haese et al., 2023).

Food waste reduction target on	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target
Primary production	n/a	10%
Processing and manufacturing	n/a	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail and consumption	15% (per capita)	50% (per capita)

3. The food supply chain

Although deliverable 1.2 explains the full supply chain model with all underlying assumptions, this chapter summarises the most important aspects of the model. Annex I describes all specific functional forms of the model, and annex II explains how the model is calibrated.

The modeled FSC distinguishes six separate stages (Figure 4). Except for the farmer who produces the food, each stage purchases a quantity from the previous stage. The purchased food is processed and prepared for resale at each stage of the supply chain until it reaches the end consumer. The processor sells the food to two different supply chain stages: food services that include hotels, restaurants, and institutions (HRI), and the retailer. The HRI sells to the consumer who eats food away from home (FAFH), while the retailer sells to the consumer who eats food at home (FAH).

*Food served at hotels, restaurants and institutions (like universities, hospitals etc.)

Figure 4: General overview of a food supply chain.

The farmer is an exception to the general explanation of the supply chain because he is producing the food instead of purchasing it from an upstream supply chain actor. The harvested quantity by the farmer is determined by the cultivar he chooses (i.e., the quantity that he could harvest per hectare without pre-harvest losses), the number of harvested hectares, and the rate of pre-harvest losses that he experiences. The farmer can reduce the pre-harvest loss rate by increasing his abatement efforts. An example of these efforts can be spraying pesticides to lower the impact of pests or spending more time on weeding.

Moreover, the farmer chooses a specific cultivar and the amount of effort to reduce pre-harvest losses subject to risk. The model distinguishes between two types of risk: the state of the weather during the growing season and the price the farmer receives for his product. Although there are more risks related to farm losses, these two types of risk are identified as the main drivers of farm losses (Minor et al., 2020).

The pre-harvest losses are simulated by equation [1] based on Lichtenberg and Zilberman (1986),

$$G^{G,B} = 1 - e^{-\eta^{G,B} X} \quad [1]$$

s.t.

$$X(x_1, x_2) = F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1-\omega)x_2^\rho)^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \quad [2]$$

where G denotes the saved rate from pre-harvest losses in either good weather (indicated by superscript G) or bad weather (indicated by superscript B). Furthermore, X is the constant elasticity of substitution (CES) aggregate [2] of pre-harvest abatement efforts x_1 and x_2 . A CES function is well equipped to capture possible complementary or substitution effects between efforts to abate pre-harvest losses. A CES function gives a modeler the possibility to directly change the elasticity of substitution between the pre-harvest abatement efforts when this is desired, for example, when a new pesticide is available to the farmer.

$\eta^{G,B}$ denotes the effectiveness of these efforts during good and bad weather, where $\eta^G > \eta^B$ such that $G^G > G^B$ for a given X. This means that the pre-harvest losses for a given level of abatement efforts are larger for bad weather than for good weather. The amount of pre-harvest losses and the price the farmer receives for his product affect how many hectares he harvests and how much of the harvested food he loses.

After the harvest, all stages of the supply chain (including the farmer) lose or waste some share of the harvested or purchased food. A part of the food that is lost or wasted is inedible, such as bones of a chicken or the core of an apple. These inedible parts of FLW are disposed of and, therefore, cannot be reduced by supply chain actors. In contrast to the inedible parts of FLW, the edible FLW can be reduced, but doing so is not free of costs. We represent the food waste abatement costs by the following functional form [3]

$$\tilde{C}_i(\alpha_i, q_i) = E_i \frac{(1 - \bar{\alpha}_i - \alpha_i)^{\tau_i}}{(q_i)^{\tau_i}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_i} - \frac{\theta_i \bar{\alpha}_i}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_i} \right), \quad [3]$$

where i indicates the stage of the supply chain, α_i denotes the edible waste rate, $\bar{\alpha}_i$ denotes the inedible waste rate and q_i is the sold quantity. Furthermore, E_i is a cost shift parameter that can be used to simulate policies or technological developments, τ_i is a parameter that indicates the shape and size of scale effects on the abatement costs and θ_i is a shape parameter that becomes important in case of an exogenous change in the inedible waste rate.

Deliverable 1.2 explains this abatement cost function in more detail, but it is important to note two extreme cases: 1) when the supply chain actor wastes the maximum rate of edible food ($\alpha_i = 1 - \bar{\alpha}_i$), the abatement costs will be 0. This follows

from the numerator in the first term, which is equal to 0 in this case. 2) when the supply chain actor does not waste any food ($\alpha_i = 0$), the abatement costs will be infinitely high. This follows from the term in parentheses on the right because $1/\alpha_i = \infty$. This property of the abatement cost function comes from the assumption that initial, low-hanging fruit FLW reductions can be achieved against relatively low costs; however, a supply chain actor must spend great efforts to save each kernel of rice during the production process, for example.

Moreover, we do not know upfront what effect a larger quantity has on the FLW abatement costs. Therefore, we do not know what value for τ_i is realistic for each stage of the supply chain (this is an empirical question for the answer to which we currently do not have sufficient data). However, we do know that when $\tau_i = -1$, there are no economies of scale with respect to the abatement cost (i.e., the average abatement cost is constant). In this case, the abatement costs change linearly in the same direction for a change in sales/consumption, holding the FLW rate constant. Permitting some economies of scale in FLW abatement, but remaining cautious about an overestimation of these effects, we calibrate all τ_i to be -0.95.

When the food is wasted, it goes to disposal services such as donations, recycling, landfill and incineration or upcycling, which makes a higher quality product from FLW. Donations, recycling and landfill and incineration compete to dispose of the FLW from the economic actors in the supply chain. They receive (i.e., the price that a supply chain stage pays) an endogenous price w to dispose of a unit of FLW. The supply functions for donations [4], recycling [5] and landfill and incineration [6] are the following:

$$D(w) = K_D w^{\sigma_D}, \quad [4]$$

$$R(w) = K_R w^{\sigma_R}, \quad [5]$$

$$L(w) = K_L w^{\sigma_L}, \quad [6]$$

where K can shift the function of a specific disposal service and σ is the elasticity of the function. The donated quantity of FLW ends up as food received for the final consumer at home.

The upcycler does not compete with the other disposal services because FLW is an input for the upcycler. He might be willing to accept a lower price or might even pay to use the FLW. Upcycling techniques are often novel, with a limited production capacity. The share of FLW of each stage of the supply chain that ends up at an upcycler (ξ_i^U) and the price of upcycling, s , are therefore modelled exogenously. The total quantity of generated FLW by the supply chain actors equals the total quantity of FLW that is handled by the disposal services.

4. Supply chain data

The data used for the simulations of the four food commodities comes from publicly accessible databases. The largest share of data is from the UK in 2012 (the latest year with complete data for the four commodities of interest), but data from other European countries or years were used when the necessary data were unavailable in the UK (see Table A1). The use of the UK data is convenient because of the alignment of their structure with the structure of the theoretical model we use and their consistency across the four commodities we use. This section provides an overview of the prices, quantities, and FLW rates along the supply chain. A detailed overview of all data used and its sources can be found in Annex III.

Table 6 gives an overview of the farmer's data. Because of the risk included in the farmer's model, there are multiple variables for each stage of nature. We observe the data for a specific state of nature for each commodity, but not for the counterfactual ones. The counterfactual price and saved rate from pre-harvest losses are determined based on the data from other years, while the counterfactual post-harvest loss rates are calibrated. The counterfactual quantities have been calibrated.

To determine the counterfactual price, we draw a trendline through the price data of other years. The observations with a higher price than the trendline are considered high-price years, and those below the trendline are low-price years. Figure 5 shows the data for milk as an example. The price of 2012 is above the trendline, meaning it was a high-price year, and the low price remains unknown. The low price is calculated by subtracting the average difference between the trendline value and the low price from the trendline value in 2012. The probability of a high-price year is calculated by dividing the number of observations with a high price by the total number of observations.

Figure 5: UK farm milk prices from 2009 – 2023 (DEFRA, 2024)

The counterfactual rate that is saved from pre-harvest losses is constructed similarly. Data over multiple years shows if 2012 was a good or bad weather year, where pre-harvest losses are larger during bad weather (i.e., the saved rate is lower). Figure 6 shows an example of pre-mature broiler losses in a chicken supply chain. The figure reveals that the broiler loss rate over 2012 is below the trendline value. Because fewer broilers were lost before maturity, the saved rate was higher, and it was a good weather year. The average increase in pre-mature losses in bad weather years is added to the trendline value of 2012 to construct the counterfactual pre-mature losses in case 2012 would have been a bad weather year.

Figure 6: Pre-mature broiler loss rate from 1990 – 2022 (Lourens and Steentjes, 2008; Agrimatie, 2018)

The prices and saved rate from pre-harvest losses are, among other data, used to calibrate the model, including the counterfactual post-harvest loss rates. The counterfactual post-harvest loss rates follow the expectations (e.g., based on Minor et al., 2020), where the least food is lost in the most favorable conditions, that is, good weather and a high price. The quantities sold by the farmer follow the same direction; most food is sold in the most favorable conditions, and the lowest quantity of food is sold in the most unfavorable conditions, that is, after bad weather and with low prices.

The inedible loss rate for the farmer is 0 for each commodity because the farmer does not separate any edible parts from the inedible parts of harvested food. This means that his post-harvest loss abatement costs are not affected by any inedible parts in the harvested food. In other words, a farmer who grows apples is unaffected by the inedible core, as they sell the whole apple. It is only when the apple reaches the consumer that the core is separated from the edible part. The consumer bears the associated costs of the inedible parts of the apple.

Table 6: Overview of key farm input data

Variable		Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Farmer					
ϕ	Probability of good weather (unit free)	0.455	0.600	0.542	0.429
ψ	Probability of a high price (unit free)	0.563	0.515	0.417	0.533
P_F^H	High selling price (£/kg)	1.095	1.145	0.163	0.280
P_F^L	Low selling price (£/kg)	0.827	0.942	0.116	0.225

$q_F^{G,H}$	Quantity produced during good weather and high prices (mmt*)	1.609	0.799	16.245	13.933
$q_F^{G,L}$	Quantity produced during good weather and low prices (mmt*)	1.599	0.787	14.110	13.899
$q_F^{B,H}$	Quantity produced during bad weather and high prices (mmt*)	1.584	0.533	12.996	13.904
$q_F^{B,L}$	Quantity produced during bad weather and low prices (mmt*)	1.575	0.412	9.094	13.870
G^G	Saved rate from pre-harvest losses during good weather (%)	0.968	0.896	0.901	0.974
G^B	Saved rate from pre-harvest losses during bad weather (%)	0.953	0.647	0.724	0.972
$\alpha_F^{G,H}$	Post-harvest edible loss rate during good weather and high prices (%)	0.043	0.142	0.020	0.029
$\alpha_F^{G,L}$	Post-harvest edible loss rate during good weather and low prices (%)	0.049	0.155	0.022	0.031
$\alpha_F^{B,H}$	Post-harvest edible loss rate during bad weather and high prices (%)	0.043	0.143	0.020	0.029
$\alpha_F^{B,L}$	Post-harvest edible loss rate during bad weather and low prices (%)	0.049	0.157	0.022	0.031
$\bar{\alpha}_F$	Post-harvest inedible loss rate (%)	0	0	0	0

*Million metric tons. Milk is in million liters.

Following the farmer data, we analyse the data of the post-farm stages of the supply chain, which is shown in Table 7. Table 7 shows how prices increase as the product moves downstream of the supply chain. The table also shows that the quantity of sold products decreases at each stage because a part of the product is wasted. In a few cases, the quantity of sold food increases when going a step downstream of the supply chain. In those cases, food is imported, which can be seen from the negative net trade in Table 7. Inedible parts of the food products are mostly found in chicken (such as bones or skin) and fruit (such as peels and stones). Only the processor in the bread supply chain observes a small share of inedible FLW, while the complete share of produced milk is perceived as edible along the supply chain. The THS sector and the retailer do not bear any costs due to the inedible parts of the food. Akin to the farmer, these sectors do not separate inedible parts from edible ones. Therefore, the inedible components do not affect their FLW abatement costs, and these inedible FLW rates are set close to zero in the supply chain model.

Table 7: Overview of key post-farm input data

	Variable	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Transport, Handling and Storage					
P_T	Selling price (£/kg)	1.150	1.430	0.515	0.400
q_T	Sold quantity (mmt*)	1.593	0.509	12.810	13.323
NT_T	Net trade of THS product (mmt*)	0	-4.251	0.224	0.253

α_T	Edible waste rate (%)	0.040	0.045	0.014	0.042
$\bar{\alpha}_T$	Inedible waste rate (%)	0	0	0	0
Processor					
P_P	Selling price (£/kg)	2.425	1.600	1.106	0.493
q_P	Sold quantity (mmt*)	1.234	4.508	11.957	12.929
NT_P	Net trade of the processor's product (mmt*)	-0.553	0	-0.329	-0.080
α_P	Edible waste rate (%)	0.115	0.027	0.026	0.012
$\bar{\alpha}_P$	Inedible waste rate (%)	0.110	0.026	0.024	0
Retailer					
P_R	Selling price (£/kg)	4.483	2.124	2.102	0.601
q_R	Sold quantity (mmt*)	1.073	3.471	7.847	11.421
α_R	Edible waste rate (%)	0.076	0.070	0.140	0.060
$\bar{\alpha}_R$	Inedible waste rate (%)	0	0	0	0
Hotels, Restaurants and Institutions					
P_H	Selling price (£/kg)	4.931	2.726	2.306	0.661
q_H	Sold quantity (mmt*)	0.606	0.622	2.791	0.851
α_H	Edible waste rate during preparation (%)	0.019	0.099	0.117	0.009
$\bar{\alpha}_H$	Inedible waste rate during preparation (%)	0.013	0.099	0	0
α_A	Edible waste rate of FAFH (%)	0.278	0.051	0.060	0.005
$\bar{\alpha}_A$	Inedible waste rate of FAFH (%)	0.098	0.051	0	0
Consumer					
q_C	Consumed quantity of FAH (mmt*)	0.663	2.176	5.556	10.382
α_C	Edible waste rate of FAH (%)	0.153	0.122	0.292	0.091
$\bar{\alpha}_C$	Inedible waste rate of FAH (%)	0.229	0.251	0	0
q_A	Consumed quantity of FAFH (mmt*)	0.378	0.558	2.623	0.847

*Million metric tons. Milk is in million liters.

5. Simulation results

The core of this deliverable only focuses on the mandatory targets in its simulations of the policy pathway reduction targets, while Annex IV shows the results for the voluntary targets in 2030. The results of the voluntary targets are in the Annex because a voluntary FLW reduction commitment can be disputed from an economic point of view (see Annex IV for a more elaborate explanation). The mandatory targets are a minimum, legally binding FLW reduction goal in each of the policy pathways, but supply chain actors can voluntarily commit to further reduce FLW. We simulate the effects of mandatory targets by imposing a tax on total (i.e., edible and inedible) FLW disposal. Taxes on the disposal of FLW simulate the increase the costs

that a supply chain actor must incur to reach the targets of policy pathways. Taxing FLW disposal is a general policy to reduce FLW because it allows economic actors to reduce their FLW in two ways: either reduce the purchased quantity or lower the FLW rate. A tax on food purchases or subsidising FLW abatement can also reduce FLW generation, but these policies directly target only one aspect of FLW: the quantity of purchased food or the FLW rate. In contrast to P2, we used sector-specific FLW disposal taxes in policy P1 and P3. For P2, we used a uniform disposal tax across the entire supply chain because its goal is to reduce FLW across the entire supply chain.

The supply chain model was able to simulate all mandatory targets, except for fruit in P2. We can explain this by taking the THS sector as an example. Economic theory prescribes that for any profit-maximising supply chain actor, the marginal revenues must equal the marginal costs. Equation 7 shows this condition for the THS sector, where the left-hand side of the equation is the marginal revenue, and the right-hand side is the marginal costs. Assume that the prices and quantity remain constant. An increase in the disposal costs (w) increases the marginal disposal cost directly. To mitigate this increase, the supply chain actor reduces its FLW rate (α_T) until the marginal abatement costs (\tilde{C}') increase faster¹ than the marginal disposal costs decrease when α_T is reduced. In this case, the total marginal costs increase (mostly because of the elastic food waste abatement cost), while the marginal revenues remain unchanged such that they are no longer equal to each other, and profit cannot be maximised by the model.

$$P_T = \frac{P_F}{B_T \delta_T} + C'(q_T) + \tilde{C}'(q_T, \alpha_T) + w \frac{(\alpha_T + \bar{\alpha}_T)}{\delta_T} \quad [7]$$

Tables 8 to 12 show the results for each policy pathway and each commodity on the necessary increase in disposal taxes (Table 8), changes in the total quantity of FLW (Table 9), the changes in edible FLW rates (Table 10), changes in quantity sold or consumed (Table 11) and changes in prices (Table 12) along the supply chain. The cells in Table 9 that are marked in green indicate the FLW reduction targets that were met. The targets that were not achieved with the model are marked in red. The closest possible results to these targets are shown when the model was not able to achieve the proposed targets.

The first result that follows from the simulations of the three policy pathways for the four commodities is that the disposal tax needs to increase significantly to achieve the goals (Table 8). P3 for milk has the lowest increase in disposal taxes; still,

¹ Note that we assume an asymptotic abatement cost function. The abatement costs are convexly increasing when the FLW rate decreases, while the disposal costs decrease linearly.

the taxes increase by 255% for the retailer and consumer. P2 is the costliest to achieve. An increase in the disposal costs of 6101% for each stage of the supply chain is necessary to achieve the FLW reduction targets for chicken in P2.

Furthermore, we observe that disposal costs for the non-taxed stages of the supply chains decrease (Table 8). In each policy pathway, the disposal taxes cause a decrease in the overall quantity of FLW across the supply chain. The total decrease in FLW lowers the demand for FLW disposal services, and, as a result, their prices decrease. The lower disposal costs lead to an increase in the edible waste rates for the non-taxed supply chain stages (Table 10). This result does not show in P2 because all stages receive a FLW disposal tax which increases their disposal costs.

The second result that follows from the simulations is the importance of inedible FLW, which is exhibited most clearly in policy pathway 3 but also has its effects in the other policy pathways. To see its effect, we compare the results of a commodity with a high inedible FLW rate, such as chicken consumption at home ($\bar{\alpha}_c = 0.229$), to a product without inedible FLW, such as milk consumption at home. Table 8 shows that the disposal tax on chicken at home must be much larger compared to the milk disposal tax at home in P3. Furthermore, Table 10 reveals that despite the higher disposal tax, the edible waste rate of chicken consumption at home does not decrease as fast as the milk waste rate at home. The inedible waste rate of chicken consumption at home causes the abatement costs of the edible waste rate to approach infinity sooner compared to the edible waste abatement costs of milk. A commodity without inedible FLW can, therefore, reach total FLW reduction targets at lower costs compared to food products with inedible FLW.

A third result that we observe based on the simulations are the cascading effects across the supply chain. These cascading effects are especially important for the processor in the fruit and bread supply chain in P1. The processors of these commodities do not require an increase in disposal costs through taxes² to meet its food loss reduction target of 10%. Although their loss rates increase because of the lower disposal costs (Table 10), the reduction in demanded quantity by the downstream stages of the supply chain (Table 11) is enough to reduce the absolute quantity of the processors' food loss. The reduction in food loss of the fruit processor even exceeds the policy pathway objective by 4.3%.

The fourth result we observe in the simulations is the substitution between food consumption at home (FAH) and away from home (FAFH). P1 and P3 show the substitution most clearly because they focus on reducing consumer's food waste at home, making FAH more costly to the consumer. FAH becomes more costly because the consumer must spend more to dispose of their food waste and must increase

² The bread processor did require a small disposal tax, but the total unit costs of FLW disposal still decreased.

the efforts to abate food waste at home. Instead of eating the more costly FAH (consumption of FAH decreases by up to 35% for chicken and fruit in P2), the consumer partly switches to FAFH. Still, the total consumption of food can decrease by up to 30% for fruit in P2 (Table 11).

Table 11 shows that the HRI sales (i.e., consumer’s FAFH purchases) increase for each commodity in P1 and P3. The increase in HRI sales does not necessarily imply that the consumer eats more FAFH (Table 11). Chicken consumption away from home slightly decreases in P1 and P3 because of the increased edible waste rate of FAFH. Recall that the disposal costs decrease for non-taxed stages of the supply chain when the total FLW generation across the supply chain decreases. This results in an increase in the FAFH waste rate, such that the quantity of chicken eaten by consumers decreases despite the larger purchases.

Finally, we look at the changes in prices (Table 12) for the four commodities across the supply chain. Generally, the food prices decrease across the supply chain in P1 and P3, except for the bread retail price in P3. The prices in P2 tend to be more unpredictable compared to other policy pathways, especially for chicken where the processor, retail and HRI sector observe a price increase. The literature indicates that several factors influence prices along the supply chain. De Gorter et al. (2021) explain that the selling price of a supply chain actor moves in the same direction as its waste rate. Furthermore, they show that the selling price of an intermediary moves in the same direction of the consumer’s waste rate when the demand for its product is inelastic. However, intermediary selling prices move in the opposite direction of the consumer’s waste rate when the demand is elastic.

A complicating factor here is that the demand elasticities change because of the tax on FLW disposal. Especially for the large shocks in P2, this could mean that a commodity with an inelastic demand in the baseline, such as chicken consumption at home, becomes a product with an elastic demand in the simulation. This results in an initially decreasing FAH waste rate and retail price because of the disposal tax, up to the point that the demand becomes elastic. A further increase of the disposal tax then still lowers the FAH waste rate, but the retailer’s price now increases. This price increase can even be larger than the initial price decrease, such that the price is higher than in the baseline.

Table 8: Required % changes in disposal costs along the supply chain for different policy pathways.

Required % change in the unit cost of disposal for the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
	Policy pathway 1			
Farmer	-32.8	-62.2	-60.1	-47.6
THS	-32.8	-62.2	-60.1	-47.6
Processor	537.2	-62.2	-15.1	124.9

Retailer	1017.2	537.8	579.9	582.4
HRI	-32.8	-62.2	-60.1	-47.6
Consumer	4967.2	2137.8	1369.9	712.4
Policy pathway 2				
Farmer	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
THS	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Processor	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Retailer	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
HRI	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Consumer	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
THS	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
Processor	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
Retailer	1585.5	743.6	425.2	255.2
HRI	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
Consumer	1585.5	743.6	425.2	255.2

Note: The costs of FLW disposal decrease for non-taxed stages of the supply chain because the demand for disposal services decreases when the total quantity of FLW decreases. Since we simulate one endogenous cost of disposal (w), the disposal costs across non-taxed stages decrease uniformly. The disposal costs increase identically in policy pathway 2 across the supply chain because we simulate a uniform tax on disposal in this scenario.

Table 9: Changes in the total quantity of FLW along the supply chain for different policy pathways.

% Change in the quantity of FLW of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer pre-harvest	16.6	-1.0	1.9	21.3
Farmer post-harvest	16.3	-8.7	5.1	13.6
THS	14.6	-10.6	4.4	12.3
Processor	-10.1	-14.3	-10.1	-10.3
Retail	-30.4	-30.7	-30.0	-30.3
HRI	14.1	17.7	12.2	21.3
FAFH	25.4	47.6	67.4	50.8
FAH	-30.1	-30.2	-30.0	-30.1
Retail + FAH	-30.1	-30.3	-30.0	-30.2
Total post-harvest supply chain	-9.3	-21.5	-18.4	-14.2
Policy pathway 2				
Farmer pre-harvest	40.9	-36.0	6.9	113.7
Farmer post-harvest	-82.7	-94.2	-78.0	-60.5
THS	-82.0	-93.7	-77.5	-59.2
Processor	-70.2	-49.3	-49.9	-55.4
Retail	-67.3	-61.6	-60.2	-52.4
HRI	-41.2	-32.4	-43.1	-39.2
FAFH	-71.0	-49.4	-80.4	-71.9
FAH	-46.7	-44.5	-49.0	-48.4
Retail + FAH	-50.4	-47.4	-53.0	-50.1
Total post-harvest supply chain	-62.5	-49.1	-47.1	-50.4
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer pre-harvest	4.5	-0.4	0.8	8.4
Farmer post-harvest	4.7	-3.2	3.5	6.1
THS	4.3	-4.1	3.2	5.6
Processor	0.7	-6.2	-3.4	3.7
Retail	-26.7	-23.5	-19.0	-16.4
HRI	6.0	7.5	5.7	9.5
FAFH	9.7	18.7	27.0	20.9
FAH	-12.6	-13.3	-12.7	-14.1
Retail + FAH	-15.1	-15.0	-14.9	-15.0
Total post-harvest supply chain	-3.8	-10.8	-9.1	-6.9

Note: Red-shaded cells indicate a policy objective was not achieved in the simulations. Green-shaded cells indicate that the policy objective was achieved in the simulation.

Table 10: Changes in edible FLW rates along the supply chain for different policy pathways.

% Change in the edible FLW rate of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Post-harvest farmer	24.8	10.4	18.4	17.5
THS	24.5	9.9	18.1	16.7
Processor	-4.3	9.1	4.7	-5.4
Retailer	-9.3	-7.6	-13.8	-25.6
HRI	9.0	7.2	5.2	10.7
Consumer FAFH	21.7	62.2	58.1	37.8
Consumer FAH	-24.1	-23.1	-15.6	-26.7
Policy pathway 2				
Post-harvest farmer	-56.3	-40.2	-67.9	-53.1
THS	-56.1	-39.2	-67.6	-52.1
Processor	-52.2	-38.1	-53.0	-48.2
Retailer	-44.1	-35.9	-37.2	-43.7
HRI	-45.9	-35.4	-38.4	-45.4
Consumer FAFH	-87.2	-81.8	-79.8	-75.0
Consumer FAH	-29.8	-29.4	-24.1	-40.6
Policy pathway 3				
Post-harvest farmer	6.5	4.6	9.1	7.5
THS	6.4	4.4	8.9	7.2
Processor	5.4	4.1	4.5	5.9
Retailer	-18.5	-14.0	-11.3	-14.1
HRI	3.9	3.3	2.6	4.9
Consumer FAFH	8.0	25.2	23.8	15.9
Consumer FAH	-10.4	-10.6	-6.1	-12.5

Table 11: Changes in sold and consumed quantities along the supply chain for different policy pathways.

% Change in sales and consumption of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	-7.8	-18.7	-11.6	-3.8
THS	-8.0	-19.0	-11.8	-4.5
Processor	-7.4	-18.3	-12.3	-5.1
Retailer	-22.6	-24.5	-17.0	-4.7
HRI	8.1	12.6	5.9	9.5
Consumer FAFH	-2.4	8.6	2.0	9.3
Consumer FAH	-18.0	-21.1	-11.7	-2.1
Total consumption of food	-12.3	-15.1	-7.3	-1.3
Policy pathway 2				
Farmer	-59.6	-89.6	-30.7	-14.8
THS	-59.4	-89.4	-30.0	-12.9
Processor	-56.2	-36.4	-29.8	-13.6
Retailer	-39.5	-38.6	-32.8	-13.1
HRI	-18.4	-14.4	-3.0	11.8
Consumer FAFH	13.4	-10.4	2.0	12.2
Consumer FAH	-35.0	-35.1	-26.2	-9.6
Total consumption of food	-17.5	-30.1	-17.1	-7.9
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-2.0	-8.2	-5.3	-1.5
THS	-2.1	-8.3	-5.4	-1.8
Processor	-2.8	-8.2	-5.7	-2.2
Retailer	-8.8	-10.2	-7.0	-1.8
HRI	3.6	5.4	2.6	4.3
Consumer FAFH	-0.1	3.8	1.1	4.2
Consumer FAH	-6.4	-8.3	-4.7	-0.6
Total consumption of food	-4.1	-5.8	-2.8	-0.2

Note: total consumption of food is FAH + FAFH.

Table 12: Changes in sale prices along the supply chain for different policy pathways.

% Change in price of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	-35.8	-13.2	-8.7	-20.3
THS	-34.6	-12.4	-7.0	-15.9
Processor	-15.8	-12.1	-6.6	-13.2
Retail	-11.8	-9.6	-2.4	-6.4
HRI	-6.5	-8.8	-3.1	-8.9
Policy pathway 2				
Farmer	-68.0	-25.9	-6.0	-44.0
THS	-62.8	-21.8	-9.7	-23.0
Processor	10.7	-11.9	-3.7	-17.8
Retail	5.8	-4.1	6.2	-4.6
HRI	23.9	20.6	9.2	-10.1
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-11.5	-5.8	-4.0	-9.1
THS	-11.1	-5.5	-3.2	-7.1
Processor	-7.4	-5.4	-3.2	-6.1
Retail	-3.4	-2.6	0.1	-2.9
HRI	-3.0	-4.0	-1.5	-4.1

6. Conclusion and discussion

The first part of the deliverable showed the simulation results of three FLW-reducing policy pathways developed for deliverable 8.1. Not only did the results of the simulations show the economic effects of a reduction in FLW at one stage of the supply chain, but the model also showed the cascading effects on other stages of the chain. The supply chain model was able to simulate every policy pathway for all four commodities, except for fruit in P2. The changes to model parameters related to P2 were too large to obtain economically valid results. We showed the closest results to the reduction target for fruit in P2.

The results of the simulations show that the disposal costs of FLW require a high tax to approach the mandatory targets of the three policy pathways. Therefore, it can be argued that solely taxing FLW disposal is not a feasible approach to achieving the FLW reduction targets of the policy pathways, and additional interventions are required. Interventions that could support further FLW reductions are, for example, the ZeroW SILLs³. Technological innovations will reduce the edible FLW abatement costs such that the quantity of FLW decreases.

The results also show the important role of inedible FLW in reducing total FLW. Therefore, the previously mentioned technological innovations that reduce the abatement costs of edible FLW could have a limited effect on reducing the total quantity of FLW for commodities with a high inedible FLW rate, such as chicken at home (see Annex IV). Increasing the price of food through taxes, such that the purchases decrease could be a more effective intervention to reduce FLW, especially for food products with a high inedible FLW rate. Future research can compare the effects of these other interventions.

The results of the simulations further show that sectors which do not experience any increase in disposal costs through taxes, increase their FLW rate when other sectors are targeted by a tax on the FLW disposal costs. A policymaker who aims to reduce FLW could prevent this by setting a FLW target which does not allow any increase of FLW for the currently untargeted stages of the supply chain, but the economic effects of such a policy are not researched for this deliverable.

The decrease in the consumption of FAH is also an important outcome to consider for the development of FLW reduction targets. Because we do not capture any heterogeneity among the consumers, we cannot draw any conclusions on which types of consumers will be most affected by the FLW reduction targets. However, we can reflect on the result that a reduction of up to 35% in consumption of FAH is a significant decrease. Although a part of this reduction is offset by eating more FAFH, the decrease in total consumption (i.e., FAH and FAFH) reaches up to 30% for fruit in P2 (given considerable

³ SILL 2's smart packaging is an innovation that will reduce the abatement costs for the consumer, because the smart packaging informs the consumer better about the freshness of a product. This reduces disposal of food where the consumer doubts whether it is still edible.

50% expected cut in food waste at consumer level). This suggests that food becomes less accessible to consumers, which can affect poorer households more compared to the wealthier households.

It is important to remember that the results of this deliverable follow from the data that was put into the model. Based on de Gorter et al. (2021), we explain that elasticities are an important driver of the results. The cascading effects upstream of the supply chain differ when the demand for a commodity is elastic or inelastic. A policymaker should, therefore, take the elasticities into account in the design of FLW-reducing policies. Furthermore, we do not take any environmental benefits into account in these simulations, but this deliverable informs a policymaker about the economic effects that FLW reductions have on the supply chain. This will support the policymaker to better weight the environmental benefits against the costs of FLW reductions.

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8. Annex I: Functional forms

To operationalize the theoretical model, we use the following functional forms with superscript $W = G, B$ where G indicates good weather and B indicates bad weather, superscripts $p = H, L$ where H indicates a high price and L indicates a low price, subscript $i = T, P, R, H$ where T indicates the THS sector, P is the processor, R is the retailer and H is the HRI sector:

Cost functions

$$c(y) = a_p A_{Fy} \frac{y}{\bar{y} - y}$$

$$\hat{C}_F^{W,p}(\alpha_{FH}^{W,p}) = A_{FH} (\alpha_{FH}^{W,p})^{\varepsilon_{FH}}$$

$$\tilde{C}_F^{W,p}(\alpha_F^{W,p}, q_F^{W,p}) = E_F \frac{(\delta_F^{W,p})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{W,p})^{\tau_F}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right)$$

$$C_i(q_i) = A_i q_i^{\varepsilon_i}$$

$$\tilde{C}_i(\alpha_i, q_i) = E_i \frac{B_i^{\tau_i} \delta_i^{\tau_i}}{q_i^{\tau_i}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_i} - \frac{\theta_i \bar{\alpha}_i}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_i} \right)$$

$$\hat{C}_H(\alpha_A, q_H) = E_A \frac{1}{q_H^{\tau_A}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta_A \bar{\alpha}_A}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_A} \right)$$

$$\tilde{C}_C(\alpha_C, q_C) = E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} \right)$$

Intermediaries' margins

$$m_i = \varepsilon_i A_i q_i^{\varepsilon_i - 1}$$

Net trade curves

$$NT_F(P_F) = H_F P_F^{\nu_F}$$

$$NT_T(P_T) = H_T P_T^{\nu_T}$$

$$NT_P(P_P) = H_P P_P^{\nu_P}$$

Farm specific functions

$$u(\pi^{W,p}) = -e^{-r\pi^{W,p}}$$

$$G^W(X) = 1 - e^{-\lambda^W X}$$

$$X = F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1 - \omega)x_2^\rho)^{\frac{1}{\rho}}$$

Equations of the empirical model with endogenous food loss/waste rates and no pre-harvest losses

The market equilibrium is found by solving 36 (= 23+13) equations for the following 36 unknowns

$$y, x_1, x_2, a_{FH}^{B,L}, a_{FH}^{B,H}, a_{FH}^{G,L}, a_{FH}^{G,L}, \alpha_{FH}^{B,L}, \alpha_{FH}^{B,H}, \alpha_{FH}^{G,L}, \alpha_{FH}^{G,L}, \alpha_T, \alpha_P, \alpha_R, \alpha_H, \alpha_A, \alpha_C, q_S^T, q_S^P, q_S^R, q_S^H, q_T, q_P, q_R, q_H, q_U, q_C, q_A, D, P_F, P_T, P_P, P_R, P_H, P_U, w$$

$$y : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial y} + (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial y} + \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial y} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial y} = 0$$

$$x_1 : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial x_1} + (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial x_1} + \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial x_1} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial x_1} = 0$$

$$x_2 : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial x_2} + (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial x_2} + \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial x_2} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial x_2} = 0$$

$$a_{FH}^{G,H} : (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \left[P_F^{G,H} \delta_F^{G,H} G^G(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{G,H})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{G,H}} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{G,H}}{q_F^{G,H}} \right)^{\tau_F} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{G,H}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) \right. \\ \left. - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) (1 - \delta_F^{G,H}) G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$a_{FH}^{G,L} : (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \left[P_F^{G,L} \delta_F^{G,L} G^G(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{G,L})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{G,L}} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{G,L}}{q_F^{G,L}} \right)^{\tau_F} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{G,L}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) \right. \\ \left. - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) (1 - \delta_F^{G,L}) G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$a_{FH}^{B,H} : \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \left[P_F^{B,H} \delta_F^{B,H} G^B(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{B,H})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{B,H}} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{B,H}}{q_F^{B,H}} \right)^{\tau_F} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{B,H}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) \right. \\ \left. - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) (1 - \delta_F^{B,H}) G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$a_{FH}^{B,L} : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \left[P_F^{B,L} \delta_F^{B,L} G^B(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{B,L})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{B,L}} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{B,L}}{q_F^{B,L}} \right)^{\tau_F} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{B,L}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) \right. \\ \left. - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) (1 - \delta_F^{B,L}) G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\alpha_F^{G,H} : (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \left[-P_F^{G,H} a_{FH}^{G,H} G^G(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{G,H})^2} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{G,H}}{q_F^{G,H}} \right)^{\tau_F} - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) a_{FH}^{G,H} G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\alpha_F^{G,L} : (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \left[-P_F^{G,L} a_{FH}^{G,L} G^G(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{G,L})^2} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{G,L}}{q_F^{G,L}} \right)^{\tau_F} - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) a_{FH}^{G,L} G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\alpha_F^{B,H} : \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \left[-P_F^{B,H} (1-l^B) a_{FH}^{B,H} G^B(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{B,H})^2} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{B,H}}{q_F^{B,H}} \right)^{\tau_F} - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) a_{FH}^{B,H} G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\alpha_F^{B,L} : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \left[-P_F^{B,L} a_{FH}^{B,L} G^B(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{B,L})^2} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{B,L}}{q_F^{B,L}} \right)^{\tau_F} - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) a_{FH}^{B,L} G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

s.t.

$$\frac{\partial \pi_F^{W,p}}{\partial y} = P_F^p \delta_F^{W,p} a_{FH}^{W,p} G^W(X) - a_p A_{Fy} \frac{\bar{y}}{(\bar{y}-y)^2} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{y} \left(\frac{\delta_F^{W,p}}{q_F^{W,p}} \right)^{\tau_F} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) (1 - \delta_F^{W,p}) a_{FH}^{W,p} G^W(X)$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_F^{W,p}}{\partial x_1} = \eta^W e^{-\eta^W X} v \omega x_1^{\rho-1} F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1-\omega) x_2^\rho)^{\frac{\nu}{\rho}-1} \delta_F^{W,p} a_{FH}^{W,p} y \left[P_F^p + \tau_F E_F \left(\frac{\delta_F^{W,p}}{q_F^{W,p}} \right)^{\tau_F+1} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) \frac{1 - \delta_F^{W,p}}{\delta_F^{W,p}} \right] - z_1$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_F^{W,p}}{\partial x_2} = \eta^W e^{-\eta^W X} v \omega x_2^{\rho-1} F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1-\omega) x_2^\rho)^{\frac{\nu}{\rho}-1} \delta_F^{W,p} a_{FH}^{W,p} y \left[P_F^p + \tau_F E_F \left(\frac{\delta_F^{W,p}}{q_F^{W,p}} \right)^{\tau_F+1} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w \xi_F^D - s \xi_F^U) \frac{1 - \delta_F^{W,p}}{\delta_F^{W,p}} \right] - z_2$$

$$q_T : P_T - \frac{P_F}{B_T \delta_T} - \varepsilon_T A_T q_T^{\varepsilon_T - 1} + \tau_T E_T \frac{B_T^{\tau_T} \delta_T^{\tau_T}}{q_T^{\tau_T + 1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_T} - \frac{\theta_T \bar{\alpha}_T}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_T} \right) - (w_{\zeta_T}^D + s_{\zeta_T}^U) \frac{1 - \delta_T}{\delta_T} = 0$$

$$q_P : P_P - \frac{P_T}{B_P \delta_P} - \varepsilon_P A_P q_P^{\varepsilon_P - 1} + \tau_P E_P \frac{B_P^{\tau_P} \delta_P^{\tau_P}}{q_P^{\tau_P + 1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_P} - \frac{\theta_P \bar{\alpha}_P}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_P} \right) - (w_{\zeta_P}^D + s_{\zeta_P}^U) \frac{1 - \delta_P}{\delta_P} = 0$$

$$q_R : P_R - \frac{P_P}{B_R \delta_R} - \varepsilon_R A_R q_R^{\varepsilon_R - 1} + \tau_R E_R \frac{B_R^{\tau_R} \delta_R^{\tau_R}}{q_R^{\tau_R + 1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_R} - \frac{\theta_R \bar{\alpha}_R}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_R} \right) - (w_{\zeta_R}^D + s_{\zeta_R}^U) \frac{1 - \delta_R}{\delta_R} = 0$$

$$q_H : P_H - \frac{P_P}{B_H \delta_H} - \varepsilon_H A_H q_H^{\varepsilon_H - 1} + \tau_H E_H \frac{B_H^{\tau_H} \delta_H^{\tau_H}}{q_H^{\tau_H + 1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_H} - \frac{\theta_H \bar{\alpha}_H}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_H} \right) + \tau_A E_A \frac{1}{q_A^{\tau_A + 1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta_A \bar{\alpha}_A}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_A} \right) - (w_{\zeta_H}^D + s_{\zeta_H}^U) \left(\frac{1}{\delta_H} - 1 \right) - (w_{\zeta_A}^D + s_{\zeta_A}^U) (1 - \delta_A) = 0$$

$$q_C : \phi_C - \lambda_C q_C - \kappa q_A + \tau_C E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C + 1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} \right) - \frac{P_U}{\delta_C} - (w_{\zeta_C}^D + s_{\zeta_C}^U) \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} = 0$$

$$q_A : \phi_A - \lambda_A q_A - \kappa q_C - \frac{P_A}{\delta_A} = 0$$

$$\alpha_T : -\frac{P_F q_T}{B_T \delta_T^2} + E_T \frac{B_T^{\tau_T} \delta_T^{\tau_T - 1}}{q_T^{\tau_T}} \left(\frac{\tau_T}{\alpha_T} - \frac{\tau_T \theta_T \bar{\alpha}_T}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_T} + \frac{\delta_T}{\alpha_T^2} \right) - (w_{\zeta_T}^D - s_{\zeta_T}^U) \frac{q_T}{\delta_T^2} = 0$$

$$\alpha_P : -\frac{P_T q_P}{B_P \delta_P^2} + E_P \frac{B_P^{\tau_P} \delta_P^{\tau_P - 1}}{q_P^{\tau_P}} \left(\frac{\tau_P}{\alpha_P} - \frac{\tau_P \theta_P \bar{\alpha}_P}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_P} + \frac{\delta_P}{\alpha_P^2} \right) - (w_{\zeta_P}^D - s_{\zeta_P}^U) \frac{q_P}{\delta_P^2} = 0$$

$$\alpha_R : -\frac{P_P q_R}{B_R \delta_R^2} + E_R \frac{B_R^{\tau_R} \delta_R^{\tau_R - 1}}{q_R^{\tau_R}} \left(\frac{\tau_R}{\alpha_R} - \frac{\tau_R \theta_R \bar{\alpha}_R}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_R} + \frac{\delta_R}{\alpha_R^2} \right) - (w_{\zeta_R}^D - s_{\zeta_R}^U) \frac{q_R}{\delta_R^2} = 0$$

$$\alpha_H : -\frac{P_P q_H}{B_H \delta_H^2} + E_H \frac{B_H^{\tau_H} \delta_H^{\tau_H - 1}}{q_H^{\tau_H}} \left(\frac{\tau_H}{\alpha_H} - \frac{\tau_H \theta_H \bar{\alpha}_H}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_H} + \frac{\delta_H}{\alpha_H^2} \right) - (w_{\zeta_H}^D - s_{\zeta_H}^U) \frac{q_H}{\delta_H^2} = 0$$

$$\alpha_A : E_A \frac{1}{\alpha_A^2 q_H^{\tau_A}} - (w_{\zeta_A}^D - s_{\zeta_A}^U) q_H = 0$$

$$\alpha_C : E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C - 1}}{q_C^{\tau_C}} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\tau_C \theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} + \frac{\delta_C}{\alpha_C^2} \right) - P_U \frac{q_C}{\delta_C^2} - (w_{\zeta_C}^D - s_{\zeta_C}^U) \frac{q_C}{\delta_C^2} = 0$$

$$q_S^T = q_F - NT_F (P_F^{pr})$$

$$q_S^P = q_T - NT_T (P_T)$$

$$q_S^R + q_S^H = q_P - NT_P (P_P)$$

$$q_R = q_U$$

$$q_T = \delta_T B_T q_S^T$$

$$q_P = \delta_P B_P q_S^P$$

$$q_R = \delta_R B_R q_S^R$$

$$q_H = \delta_H B_H q_S^H$$

$$q_C = \delta_C (q_U + \mu D)$$

$$q_A = \delta_A q_H$$

$$D = D(w)$$

$$P_R = P_U$$

$$R(w) + D(w) + L(w) = \zeta_F^D \frac{(1 - \delta_F)}{\delta_F} q_F + \zeta_T^D (1 - \delta_T) B_T q_S^T + \zeta_P^D (1 - \delta_P) B_P q_S^P + \zeta_R^D (1 - \delta_R) B_R q_S^R + \zeta_H^D (1 - \delta_H) B_H q_S^H + \zeta_A^D (1 - \delta_A) q_H + \zeta_C^D (1 - \delta_C) (q_U + \mu D)$$

9. Annex II: Calibration of the model

The farmer's model:

The following 13 conditions need to hold to calibrate the farmer's model.

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial y} : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial y} + (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial y} + \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial y} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial y} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial x_1} : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial x_1} + (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial x_1} + \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial x_1} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial x_1} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial x_2} : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial x_2} + (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial x_2} + \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial x_2} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial x_2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial a_{FH}^{G,H}} = (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \left[P_F^{G,H} \delta_F^{G,H} G^G(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{G,H})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{G,H}} \frac{(\delta_F^{G,H})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{G,H})^{\tau_F}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{G,H}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) (1 - \delta_F^{G,H}) G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial a_{FH}^{G,L}} = (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \left[P_F^{G,L} \delta_F^{G,L} G^G(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{G,L})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{G,L}} \frac{(\delta_F^{G,L})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{G,L})^{\tau_F}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{G,L}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) (1 - \delta_F^{G,L}) G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial a_{FH}^{B,H}} = \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \left[P_F^{B,H} \delta_F^{B,H} G^B(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{B,H})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{B,H}} \frac{(\delta_F^{B,H})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{B,H})^{\tau_F}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{B,H}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) (1 - \delta_F^{B,H}) G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial a_{FH}^{B,L}} = \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \left[P_F^{B,L} \delta_F^{B,L} G^B(X) y - \varepsilon_{FH} A_{FH} (a_{FH}^{B,L})^{\varepsilon_{FH}-1} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{a_{FH}^{B,L}} \frac{(\delta_F^{B,L})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{B,L})^{\tau_F}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{B,L}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) (1 - \delta_F^{B,L}) G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_F^{G,H}} : (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{G,H}} \left[-P_F^H a_{FH}^{G,H} G^G(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{G,H})^2} \frac{(\delta_F^{G,H})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{G,H})^{\tau_F}} - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) a_{FH}^{G,H} G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_F^{G,L}} : (1-\psi) \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{G,L}} \left[-P_F^L a_{FH}^{G,L} G^G(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{G,L})^2} \frac{(\delta_F^{G,L})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{G,L})^{\tau_F}} - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) a_{FH}^{G,L} G^G(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_F^{B,H}} : \psi(1-\varphi) re^{-r\pi_F^{B,H}} \left[-P_F^H (1-l^B) a_{FH}^{B,H} G^B(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{B,H})^2} \frac{(\delta_F^{B,H})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{B,H})^{\tau_F}} - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) a_{FH}^{B,H} G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_F^{B,L}} : \psi \varphi re^{-r\pi_F^{B,L}} \left[-P_F^L a_{FH}^{B,L} G^B(X) y + \frac{E_F}{(\alpha_F^{B,L})^2} \frac{(\delta_F^{B,L})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{B,L})^{\tau_F}} - (w_{\zeta_F}^D - s_{\zeta_F}^U) a_{FH}^{B,L} G^B(X) y \right] = 0$$

$$G^G(X) = 1 - e^{-\eta^G X}$$

$$G^B(X) = 1 - e^{-\eta^B X}$$

s.t.

$$\frac{\partial \pi_F^{W,p}}{\partial y} = P_F^p \delta_F^{W,p} a_{FH}^{W,p} G^W(X) - a_p A_{Fy} \frac{\bar{y}}{(\bar{y} - y)^2} + \tau_F \frac{E_F}{y} \frac{(\delta_F^{W,p})^{\tau_F}}{(q_F^{W,p})^{\tau_F}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F^D} - s_{\zeta_F^U}) (1 - \delta_F^{W,p}) a_{FH}^{W,p} G^W(X)$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_F^{W,p}}{\partial x_1} = \eta^W e^{-\eta^W X} v \omega x_1^{\rho-1} F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1-\omega)x_2^\rho)^{\frac{v}{\rho}-1} \delta_F^{W,p} a_{FH}^{W,p} y \left[P_F^p + \tau_F E_F \frac{(\delta_F^{W,p})^\tau}{(q_F^{W,p})^{\tau+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F^D} - s_{\zeta_F^U}) \frac{1 - \delta_F^{W,p}}{\delta_F^{W,p}} \right] - z_1$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_F^{W,p}}{\partial x_2} = \eta^W e^{-\eta^W X} v \omega x_2^{\rho-1} F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1-\omega)x_2^\rho)^{\frac{v}{\rho}-1} \delta_F^{W,p} a_{FH}^{W,p} y \left[P_F^p + \tau_F E_F \frac{(\delta_F^{W,p})^\tau}{(q_F^{W,p})^{\tau+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_F^{W,p}} - \frac{\theta_F \bar{\alpha}_F}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_F} \right) - (w_{\zeta_F^D} - s_{\zeta_F^U}) \frac{1 - \delta_F^{W,p}}{\delta_F^{W,p}} \right] - z_2$$

$$X = F(\omega x_1^\rho + (1-\omega)x_2^\rho)^{\frac{v}{\rho}}$$

The following 13 parameters are calibrated with the 13 equations:

$$A_{Fy}, A_{FH}, E_F, \tau_F, \omega, \eta^G, \eta^B, a_{FH}^{G,L}, a_{FH}^{B,H}, a_{FH}^{B,L}, \alpha_F^{G,L}, \alpha_F^{B,H}, \alpha_F^{B,L}$$

The intermediaries' models:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_T &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon_T q_T^{\varepsilon_T-1}} \left[P_T - \frac{P_F}{B_T \delta_T} + \tau_T E_T \frac{B_T^{\tau_T} \delta_T^{\tau_T}}{q_T^{\tau_T+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_T} - \frac{\theta_T \bar{\alpha}_T}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_T} \right) - (w_{\zeta_T^D} - s_{\zeta_T^U}) \frac{1 - \delta_T}{\delta_T} \right] \\
 A_P &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon_P q_P^{\varepsilon_P-1}} \left[P_P - \frac{P_T}{B_P \delta_P} + \tau_P E_P \frac{B_P^{\tau_P} \delta_P^{\tau_P}}{q_P^{\tau_P+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_P} - \frac{\theta_P \bar{\alpha}_P}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_P} \right) - (w_{\zeta_P^D} - s_{\zeta_P^U}) \frac{1 - \delta_P}{\delta_P} \right] \\
 A_R &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon_R q_R^{\varepsilon_R-1}} \left[P_R - \frac{P_P}{B_R \delta_R} + \tau_R E_R \frac{B_R^{\tau_R} \delta_R^{\tau_R}}{q_R^{\tau_R+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_R} - \frac{\theta_R \bar{\alpha}_R}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_R} \right) - (w_{\zeta_R^D} - s_{\zeta_R^U}) \frac{1 - \delta_R}{\delta_R} \right] \\
 A_H &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon_H q_H^{\varepsilon_H-1}} \left[P_H - \frac{P_P}{B_H \delta_H} + \tau_H E_H \frac{B_H^{\tau_H} \delta_H^{\tau_H}}{q_H^{\tau_H+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_H} - \frac{\theta_H \bar{\alpha}_H}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_H} \right) + \tau_A E_A \frac{1}{q_H^{\tau_A+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta_A \bar{\alpha}_A}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_A} \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - (w_{\zeta_H^D} - s_{\zeta_H^U}) \left(\frac{1}{\delta_H} - 1 \right) - (w_{\zeta_A^D} - s_{\zeta_A^U}) (1 - \delta_A) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$E_T = \left[\frac{P_F q_T}{B_T \delta_T^2} + (w_{\zeta_T^D} - s_{\zeta_T^U}) \frac{q_T}{\delta_T} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_T}{\delta_T} \right) \right] \frac{q_T^{\tau_T}}{B_T^{\tau_T} \delta_T^{\tau_T-1} \left(\frac{\tau_T}{\alpha_T} - \frac{\tau_T \theta_T \bar{\alpha}_T}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_T} + \frac{\delta_T}{\alpha_T^2} \right)}$$

$$E_P = \left[\frac{P_T q_P}{B_P \delta_P^2} + (w_{\zeta_P^D} - s_{\zeta_P^U}) \frac{q_P}{\delta_P} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_P}{\delta_P} \right) \right] \frac{q_P^{\tau_P}}{B_P^{\tau_P} \delta_P^{\tau_P-1} \left(\frac{\tau_P}{\alpha_P} - \frac{\tau_P \theta_P \bar{\alpha}_P}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_P} + \frac{\delta_P}{\alpha_P^2} \right)}$$

$$E_R = \left[\frac{P_P q_R}{B_R \delta_R^2} + (w_{\zeta_R^D} - s_{\zeta_R^U}) \frac{q_R}{\delta_R} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_R}{\delta_R} \right) \right] \frac{q_R^{\tau_R}}{B_R^{\tau_R} \delta_R^{\tau_R-1} \left(\frac{\tau_R}{\alpha_R} - \frac{\tau_R \theta_R \bar{\alpha}_R}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_R} + \frac{\delta_R}{\alpha_R^2} \right)}$$

$$E_H := -\frac{P_P q_H}{B_H \delta_H^2} + E_H \frac{B_H^{\tau_H} \delta_H^{\tau_H-1}}{q_H^{\tau_H}} \left(\frac{\tau_H}{\alpha_H} - \frac{\tau_H \theta_H \bar{\alpha}_H}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_H} + \frac{\delta_H}{\alpha_H^2} \right) - (w_{\zeta_H^D} - s_{\zeta_H^U}) \frac{q_H}{\delta_H^2} = 0$$

$$E_A = \alpha_A^2 q_H^{\tau_A+1} (w_{\zeta_A^D} - s_{\zeta_A^U})$$

$$H_F = \frac{N T_F}{P_F^{\nu_F}}$$

$$H_T = \frac{N T_T}{P_T^{\nu_T}}$$

$$H_P = \frac{N T_P}{P_P^{\nu_P}}$$

The consumer's model:

The consumer's model maximizes the following function:

$$\max L(q_C, q_A, \alpha_C) = \phi_C q_C + \phi_A q_A - \frac{1}{2}(\lambda_C q_C^2 + \lambda_A q_A^2) - \kappa q_C q_A - E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} \right) - P_U \frac{q_C}{\delta_C} - P_A \frac{q_A}{\delta_A} - (w_{\xi_C^D} - s_{\xi_C^U})(1 - \delta_C) \frac{q_C}{\delta_C}$$

where $\delta_C = 1 - \alpha_C - \bar{\alpha}_C$ and $q_C = \delta_C (q_U + \mu D)$.

This model gives the following first-order conditions:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial q_C} = \phi_C - \lambda_C q_C - \kappa q_A + \tau_C E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} \right) - \frac{P_U}{\delta_C} - (w_{\xi_C^D} - s_{\xi_C^U}) \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial q_A} = \phi_A - \lambda_A q_A - \kappa q_C - \frac{P_A}{\delta_A} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \alpha_C} = E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C-1}}{q_C^{\tau_C}} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\tau_C \theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{(1 - \bar{\alpha}_C)} + \frac{\delta_C}{\alpha_C^2} \right) - P_U \frac{q_C}{\delta_C^2} - (w_{\xi_C^D} - s_{\xi_C^U}) \frac{q_C}{\delta_C} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} \right) = 0$$

E_C can be substituted out of these first-order conditions, which gives:

$$E_C = \frac{q_C^{\tau_C}}{\delta_C^{\tau_C} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\delta_C \alpha_C} - \frac{\tau_C \theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{\delta_C (1 - \bar{\alpha}_C)} + \frac{1}{\alpha_C^2} \right)} \left(\frac{P_U q_C}{\delta_C^2} + (w_{\xi_C^D} - s_{\xi_C^U}) \frac{q_C}{\delta_C} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} \right) \right)$$

This leaves us with 6 parameters require calibration: $\phi_C, \phi_A, \lambda_C, \lambda_A, \kappa$ and τ_C . These parameters are calibrated by using the first-order conditions, the own-price elasticities, and the cross-prices elasticities of q_C and q_A .

To determine the equations for the elasticities, we first take the total derivatives of the first-order conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[-\lambda_c - \tau_c^2 E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c}}{q_c^{\tau_c+2}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_c} - \frac{\theta_c \bar{\alpha}_c}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_c} \right) - \tau_c E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c}}{q_c^{\tau_c+2}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_c} - \frac{\theta_c \bar{\alpha}_c}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_c} \right) \right] dq_c - \kappa dq_A \\ & + \left[-\tau_c^2 E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c-1}}{q_c^{\tau_c+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_c} - \frac{\theta_c \bar{\alpha}_c}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_c} \right) - \tau_c E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c}}{q_c^{\tau_c+1}} \frac{1}{\alpha_c^2} - \frac{P_U}{\delta_c^2} - \frac{w_{\zeta_c^D} - s_{\zeta_c^U}}{\delta_c} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_c}{\delta_c} \right) \right] d\alpha_c = \frac{1}{\delta_c} dP_U \\ & -\kappa dq_c - \lambda_A dq_A = \frac{1}{\delta_A} dP_A \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[-\tau_c^2 E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c-1}}{q_c^{\tau_c+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_c} - \frac{\theta_c \bar{\alpha}_c}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_c} \right) - \tau_c E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c}}{q_c^{\tau_c+1}} \frac{1}{\alpha_c^2} - \frac{P_U}{\delta_c^2} - \frac{w_{\zeta_c^D} - s_{\zeta_c^U}}{\delta_c} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_c}{\delta_c} \right) \right] dq_c \\ & + \left[-\tau_c (\tau_c - 1) E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c-2}}{q_c^{\tau_c}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_c} - \frac{\theta_c \bar{\alpha}_c}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_c} \right) - 2E_c \tau_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c-1}}{q_c^{\tau_c} \alpha_c^2} - 2E_c \frac{\delta_c^{\tau_c}}{q_c^{\tau_c} \alpha_c^3} - 2 \frac{q_c P_U}{\delta_c^3} - 2(w_{\zeta_c^D} - s_{\zeta_c^U}) \frac{q_c}{\delta_c^2} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_c}{\delta_c} \right) \right] d\alpha_c = \frac{q_c}{\delta_c^2} dP_U \end{aligned}$$

Which can be rewritten as:

$$a_{11} dq_c + a_{12} dq_A + a_{13} d\alpha_c = dP_U$$

$$a_{21} dq_c + a_{22} dq_A + a_{23} d\alpha_c = dP_A$$

$$a_{31} dq_c + a_{32} dq_A + a_{33} d\alpha_c = dP_U$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{11} &= -\delta_C q_C \lambda_C - \tau_C (\tau_C + 1) E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C+1}}{q_C^{\tau_C+2}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta \bar{\alpha}_U}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_U} \right) \\
 a_{12} &= -\delta_C \kappa \\
 a_{13} &= -\tau_C E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C+1}} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\tau_C \theta \bar{\alpha}_U}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_U} + \frac{\delta_C}{\alpha_C^2} \right) - \frac{P_U}{\delta_C} - (w \xi_C^D - s \xi_C^U) \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} \right) \\
 a_{21} &= -\delta_A \kappa \\
 a_{22} &= -\delta_A \lambda_A \\
 a_{23} &= 0 \\
 a_{31} &= -\tau_C E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C+1}}{q_C^{\tau_C+2}} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\tau_C \theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} + \frac{\delta_C}{\alpha_C^2} \right) - \frac{P_U}{q_C} - (w \xi_C^D - s \xi_C^U) \frac{\delta_C}{q_C} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} \right) \\
 a_{32} &= 0 \\
 a_{33} &= -\tau_C (\tau_C - 1) E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} \right) - 2 E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C+1}}{q_C^{\tau_C+1}} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\alpha_C^2} + \frac{\delta_C}{\alpha_C^3} \right) - \frac{2 P_U}{\delta_C} - 2 (w \xi_C^D - s \xi_C^U) \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

This can be written into a matrix notation, which gives:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} dq_C \\ dq_A \\ d\alpha_C \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} dP_U \\ dP_A \\ dP_U \end{pmatrix}$$

Then, using Cramer's rule, we can determine the elasticities:

$$\det = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & 0 \\ a_{31} & 0 & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11} a_{22} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{22} a_{31} - a_{12} a_{21} a_{33}$$

$$dq_C = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} dP_U & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ dP_A & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ dP_U & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}}{\det}, dq_A = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & dP_U & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & dP_A & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & dP_U & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}}{\det}$$

$$\frac{dq_C}{dP_U} = \frac{a_{22} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{22}}{\det}, \frac{dq_A}{dP_U} = \frac{a_{13} a_{21} - a_{21} a_{33}}{\det}$$

$$\frac{dq_C}{dP_A} = -\frac{a_{12} a_{33}}{\det}, \frac{dq_A}{dP_A} = \frac{a_{11} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{31}}{\det}$$

$$\chi_U = \frac{dq_C}{dP_U} \frac{P_U}{q_C} = \left(\frac{a_{22} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{22}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_U}{q_C}$$

$$\chi_H = \frac{dq_A}{dP_A} \frac{P_A}{q_A} = \left(\frac{a_{11} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{31}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_A}{q_A}$$

$$\chi_{HU} = \frac{dq_A}{dP_U} \frac{P_U}{q_A} = \left(\frac{a_{13} a_{21} - a_{21} a_{33}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_U}{q_A}$$

$$\chi_{UH} = \frac{dq_C}{dP_A} \frac{P_A}{q_C} = \left(-\frac{a_{12} a_{33}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_A}{q_C}$$

These elasticities, together with two first-order conditions and the equation for E_C , calibrate the model:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_C - \lambda_C q_C - \kappa q_A + \tau_C E_C \frac{\delta_C^{\tau_C}}{q_C^{\tau_C+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_C} - \frac{\theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_C} \right) - \frac{P_U}{\delta_C} - (w \xi_C^D - s \xi_C^U) \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} &= 0 \\ \phi_A - \lambda_A q_A - \kappa q_C - \frac{P_A}{\delta_A} &= 0 \\ \chi_U &= \left(\frac{a_{22} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{22}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_U}{q_C} \\ \chi_H &= \left(\frac{a_{11} a_{33} - a_{13} a_{31}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_A}{q_A} \\ \chi_{HU} &= \left(\frac{a_{13} a_{21} - a_{21} a_{33}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_U}{q_A} \\ \chi_{UH} &= \left(-\frac{a_{12} a_{33}}{\det} \right) \frac{P_U}{q_C} \\ E_C &= \frac{q_C^{\tau_C}}{\delta_C^{\tau_C} \left(\frac{\tau_C}{\delta_C \alpha_C} - \frac{\tau_C \theta_C \bar{\alpha}_C}{\delta_C (1 - \bar{\alpha}_C)} + \frac{1}{\alpha_C^2} \right)} \left(\frac{P_U q_C}{\delta_C^2} + (w \xi_C^D + s \xi_C^U) \frac{q_C}{\delta_C} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \delta_C}{\delta_C} \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

10. Annex III: Input data for the four commodities

Table A1. Baseline value of the chicken farmer's model

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
EU	The expected utility of the farmer based on the states of nature and their probabilities.	-1.798	-0.246	-0.040	-0.005	Result from calibration.
$\pi_F^{G,H}$	The farmer's profit in the case of good weather and high prices.	1.37	0.416	1.361	2.925	Result from calibration.
$\pi_F^{G,L}$	The farmer's profit in the case of good weather and low prices.	0.94	0.255	0.623	2.16	Result from calibration.
$\pi_F^{B,H}$	The farmer's profit in the case of bad weather and high prices.	1.344	0.205	0.862	2.917	Result from calibration.
$\pi_F^{B,L}$	The farmer's profit in the case of bad weather and low prices.	0.921	0.109	0.349	2.154	Result from calibration.
r	Parameter that indicates the risk aversion of the farmer.	-0.497	6.07	6.07	2.23	Pennings and Smidts (2000); Gardebroek, 2006; Vollenweider et al., 2011.
$G^G(X)$	A function that translates the aggregate of efforts to reduce pre-harvest losses into the share of preserved potential yield in the case of good weather.	0.968	0.8959	0.901	0.974	Lourens and Steentjes, 2008; Agrimatie, 2018; DEFRA, 2019, 2024a; AHDB, 2024b; Mastitis Control Plan, 2024;
$G^B(X)$	A function that translates the aggregate of efforts to reduce pre-harvest losses into the share of preserved potential yield in the case of bad weather.	0.953	0.6469	0.724	0.972	Hagnestam-Nielsen et al., 2009; Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015.
F	The productivity of pre-harvest reduction efforts.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
η^G	Effectiveness of pre-harvest reduction efforts in the case of good weather.	6.146	2.433	1.196	15.907	Calibrated.
η^B	Effectiveness of pre-harvest reduction efforts in the case of bad weather.	5.472	1.12	0.665	15.583	Calibrated.
x_1	Pre-harvest abatement effort 1.	0.026	0.0013	260	0.188	DEFRA, 2019; Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015; Agrimatie, n.d.a.
x_2	Pre-harvest abatement effort 2.	0.036	0.0008	2	0.044	DEFRA, 2019; Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015; Vermeij et al., 2023.
X	The aggregate of pre-harvest reduction efforts.	0.56	0.93	1.932	0.230	Result from calibration.
z_1	Unit cost of pre-harvest abatement effort 1, x_1 .	1	1	0.0002	1	Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015; Normalized.
z_2	Unit cost of pre-harvest abatement effort 2, x_2 .	0.182	1	0.0001	1	Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015; Vermeij et al., 2023; normalized.
ω	The share parameter between x_1 and x_2 .	0.802	0.621	0.994	0.788	Calibrated.
ν	The degree of homogeneity of X , the aggregate of pre-harvest reduction efforts.	0.162	0.011	0.119	0.749	Assumed.
σ_F	The substitution elasticity between x_1 and x_2 .	1.111	1.111	1.111	1.11	Assumed.
ρ	A CES substitution parameter that determines σ_F , the substitution elasticity between x_1 and x_2 .	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	Assumed.
\bar{y}	Cultivar or breed with the theoretically highest possible yield per hectare that is available on the market.	2.8	34.1	10	10	Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015; Vermeij et al., 2023; assumed.

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
y	By the farmer chosen cultivar or breed in theoretically possible yield per hectare or per animal.	2.3	31	9.2	8.2	DEFRA, 2019, 2024c; Agrimatie, 2023; AHDB, 2023, 2024b; Mastitis Control Plan, 2024; Hagnestam-Nielsen et al., 2009; Spruijt and Van der Voort, 2015; assumed.
c_0	The costs that are related to planting a crop, other than the seed costs, or fixed costs per animal.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
A_{Fy}	Cultivar cost shift parameter.	0.078	0.131	0.004	0.068	Calibrated.
a_p	The number of planted hectares or raised animals.	0.756	0.034	2	1.796	DEFRA, 2019, 2024a; AHDB, 2012, 2014, 2015a, 2015b, 2016, 2018, 2024a.
$a_{FH}^{G,H}$	The number of harvested hectares in the case of good weather and high prices.	0.756	0.034	2	1.796	
$a_{FH}^{G,L}$	The number of harvested hectares in the case of good weather and low prices.	0.756	0.031	1.741	1.796	DEFRA, 2019, 2024a; Equal to a_p ; Calibrated.
$a_{FH}^{B,H}$	The number of harvested hectares in the case of bad weather and high prices.	0.756	0.034	1.992	1.796	
$a_{FH}^{B,L}$	The number of harvested hectares in the case of bad weather and low prices.	0.756	0.024	1.397	1.796	
A_{FH}	Harvest cost shift parameter.	0	265.8	0.255	0	Calibrated.
ε_{FH}	Harvest cost elasticity parameter.	2	2	2	2	Assumed.

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Sources
P_F^H	Selling price of the farmer in the case of high prices.	1.095	1.145	0.163	0.280	AHDB, 2012, 2014, 2015a, 2015b, 2016, 2018; DEFRA, 2019, 2024a, 2024b;
P_F^L	Selling price of the farmer in the case of low prices.	0.827	0.942	0.116	0.225	Agrimatie, n.d.b.
$\alpha_F^{G,H}$	Edible post-harvest farm loss rate in the case of good weather and high prices.	0.043	0.142	0.020	0.029	Beausang et al., 2017; Gustavsson et al., 2011;
$\alpha_F^{G,L}$	Edible post-harvest farm loss rate in the case of good weather and low prices.	0.049	0.155	0.022	0.031	Hartikainen et al., 2017, 2018; Redlingshöfer et al., 2017; Tesco PLC, 2018a, 2018b; WRAP, 2011c, 2017a; Calibrated.
$\alpha_F^{B,H}$	Edible post-harvest farm loss rate in the case of bad weather and high prices.	0.043	0.143	0.020	0.029	
$\alpha_F^{B,L}$	Edible post-harvest farm loss rate in the case of bad weather and low prices.	0.049	0.157	0.022	0.031	
$\bar{\alpha}_F$	Inedible post-harvest farm loss rate.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
$\delta_F^{G,H}$	Sold rate of the harvested quantity in the case of good weather and high prices.	0.957	0.858	0.980	0.971	$=1 - \alpha_F^{G,H} - \bar{\alpha}_F$
$\delta_F^{G,L}$	Sold rate of the harvested quantity in the case of good weather and low prices.	0.951	0.845	0.978	0.969	$=1 - \alpha_F^{G,L} - \bar{\alpha}_F$
$\delta_F^{B,H}$	Sold rate of the harvested quantity in the case of bad weather and high prices.	0.957	0.857	0.980	0.971	$=1 - \alpha_F^{B,H} - \bar{\alpha}_F$
$\delta_F^{B,L}$	Sold rate of the harvested quantity in the case of bad weather and low prices.	0.951	0.843	0.978	0.969	$=1 - \alpha_F^{B,L} - \bar{\alpha}_F$
θ_F	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food loss reductions on the edible food loss abatement cost of the farmer.	1000	1000	1000	1000	Assumed.
τ_F	The negative scale elasticity of post-harvest food loss abatement.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Calibrated.

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
E_F	Post harvest food loss abatement cost shift parameter.	0.002	0.025	0.0001	0.0004	Calibrated.
$q_F^{G,H}$	The quantity that is harvested by the farmer in the case of good weather and high price.	1.609	0.799	16.245	13.933	AHDB, 2012, 2014, 2015a, 2015b, 2016, 2018, 2024a, 2024b; DEFRA, 2019, 2024a, 2024c; Mastitis Control Plan, 2024;
$q_F^{G,L}$	The quantity that is harvested by the farmer in the case of good weather and low prices.	1.599	0.787	14.110	13.899	Hagnestam-Nielsen et al., 2009;
$q_F^{B,H}$	The quantity that is harvested by the farmer in the case of bad weather and high prices.	1.584	0.533	12.996	13.904	Result from calibration.
$q_F^{B,L}$	The quantity that is harvested by the farmer in the case of bad weather and low prices.	1.575	0.412	9.094	13.870	
ξ_F^D	The share of farm waste that goes to a disposition destination.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_F^U	The share of farm waste that is upcycled.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
ψ	The probability of high price.	0.563	0.515	0.417	0.533	Agrimatie, n.d.b; DEFRA, 2019, 2024a, 2024b. Lourens and Steentjes, 2008; Agrimatie, 2018;
φ	The probability good weather.	0.455	0.6	0.542	0.429	DEFRA, 2019, 2024a; AHDB, 2024b.

Table A2. Baseline data of the THS model

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
π_T	Profit of the THS sector.	0.016	0.027	1.466	0.373	Result from calibration.
P_T	Selling price of the THS sector.	1.15	1.43	0.515	0.4	HMRC, 2018.
q_T	Sold quantity by the THS sector.	1.593	0.509	12.810	13.323	$= \delta_T q_S^T$
q_S^T	Purchased quantity of food by the THS sector. This is either purchased from the farmer or imported.	1.609	0.533	12.996	13.906	$= q_F - NT_F$
B_T	Transformation coefficient of the THS sector that can be used to capture shrinkage during the production process.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_T^D	Share of THS loss that goes to dispositions.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_T^U	Share of THS loss that will be upcycled.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
A_T	THS production cost shift parameter.	0.016	0.158	0.064	0.016	Calibrated.
ε_T	Parameter that is used to indicate the production cost elasticity of the THS sector.	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	Assumed.
α_T	The edible food loss rate of the THS sector.	0.01	0.045	0.014	0.042	Beausang et al., 2017; Gustavsson et al., 2011; Hartikainen et al., 2017, 2018; Redlingshöfer et al., 2017; Tesco PLC, 2018a, 2018b; WRAP, 2011c, 2017a.
$\bar{\alpha}_T$	The inedible food loss rate of the THS sector.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
δ_T	Used rate of food by the THS sector.	0.99	0.955	0.986	0.958	$= 1 - \alpha_T - \bar{\alpha}_T$

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
θ_T	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food loss reductions on the edible food loss abatement cost of the THS.	1000	1000	1000	1000	Assumed.
E_T	Food loss abatement cost shift parameter for the THS sector.	0.0001	0.003	0.00006	0.001	Calibrated.
τ_T	Negative food loss abatement scale elasticity of the THS.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Assumed.
NT_T	Net trade of the THS sector.	0	-4.251	0.224	0.253	HMRC, 2018.
H_T	Net trade curve shift parameter of the THS sector.	0	-2.486	0.083	0.064	Calibrated.
ν_T	Net trade elasticity parameter of the THS sector.	-1.5	1.5	-1.5	-1.5	Assumed.

Table A3. Baseline data of the processor's model

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
π_p	Profit of the processor.	0.268	0.051	2.152	0.351	Result from calibration.
P_p	Selling price of the processor.	2.425	1.6	1.106	0.493	HMRC, 2018.
q_p	Sold quantity by the processor.	1.234	4.508	11.957	12.292	$= q_s^p \cdot \delta_p$
q_s^p	Purchased quantity of food by the processor. This is either purchased from the THS sector or imported.	1.593	4.76	12.586	13.070	$= q_T - NT_T$
B_p	Transformation coefficient of the processor that can be used to capture shrinkage during the production process.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_p^D	Share of processor loss that goes to dispositions.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_p^U	Share of processor loss that will be upcycled.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
A_p	Production cost shift parameter of the processor.	0.412	0.013	0.105	0.015	Calibrated.
ε_p	Parameter that is used to indicate the production cost elasticity of the processor.	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	Assumed.
α_p	The edible food loss rate of the processor.	0.115	0.027	0.026	0.011	Gustavsson et al., 2011; Hartikainen et al., 2018; Redlingshöfer et al., 2017; Tesco PLC, 2018a, 2018b; WRAP, 2011c, 2016, 2017a; Goucher et al, 2017.
$\bar{\alpha}_p$	The inedible food loss rate of the processor.	0.11	0.026	0.024	0	WRAP 2018a; assumed.
δ_p	Used rate of food by the processor.	0.775	0.947	0.95	0.989	$= 1 - \alpha_p - \bar{\alpha}_p$

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
θ_p	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food loss reductions on the edible food loss abatement cost of the processor.	9.091	38.462	41.667	1000	Assumed.
E_p	Food loss abatement cost shift parameter for the processor.	0.025	0.001	0.001	0.00007	Calibrated.
τ_p	Negative food loss abatement scale elasticity of the processor.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Assumed.
NT_p	Net trade of the processor.	-0.533	0	-0.329	-0.080	HMRC, 2018.
H_p	Net trade curve shift parameter of the processor.	-0.146	0	-0.282	-0.231	Calibrated.
ν_p	Net trade elasticity parameter of the processor.	1.5	-1.5	1.5	1.5	Assumed.

Table A4. Baseline data of the retailer's model

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
π_R	Profit of the retailer.	0.574	0.283	1.439	0.099	Result from calibration.
P_R	Selling price of the retailer.	4.483	2.124	2.102	0.601	DEFRA and ONS, 2017.
q_R	Sold quantity by the retailer.	1.074	3.471	7.847	11.421	$= q_S^R \cdot \delta_R$
q_S^R	Purchased quantity of food by the retailer. This is either purchased from the processor or imported.	1.162	3.732	9.124	12.150	DEFRA and ONS, 2017.
B_R	Transformation coefficient of the retailer that can be used to capture shrinkage during the production process.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_R^D	Share of retailer waste that goes to dispositions.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_R^U	Share of retailer waste that will be upcycled.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
A_R	Production cost shift parameter of the retailer.	1.054	0.095	0.139	0.006	Calibrated.
ε_R	Production cost elasticity of the retailer.	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	Assumed.
α_R	The edible food waste rate of the retailer.	0.076	0.070	0.140	0.060	WRAP, 2016.
$\bar{\alpha}_R$	The inedible food waste rate of the retailer.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
δ_R	Used rate of food by the retailer.	0.924	0.930	0.860	0.940	$= 1 - \alpha_R - \bar{\alpha}_R$
θ_R	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food waste reductions on the edible food loss abatement cost of the retailer.	1000	1000	1000	1000	Assumed.
E_R	Food waste abatement cost shift parameter for the retailer.	0.017	0.010	0.035	0.003	Calibrated.
τ_R	Negative food waste abatement scale elasticity of the retailer.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Assumed.

Table A5. Baseline data of the Hotels, Restaurants and Institutions sector's model

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
π_H	Profit of the HRI sector.	0.446	0.084	0.772	0.044	Result from calibration.
P_H	Selling price of the HRI sector.	4.931	2.726	2.306	0.661	Assumed.
q_H	Sold quantity by the HRI sector.	0.606	0.622	2.791	0.851	$= q_S^H \cdot \delta_H$
q_S^H	Purchased quantity of food by the HRI sector. This is either purchased from the processor or imported.	0.626	0.775	3.161	0.859	DEFRA and ONS, 2017.
B_H	Transformation coefficient of the HRI sector that can be used to capture shrinkage during the production process.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_H^D	Share of HRI sector waste that goes to dispositions.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
ξ_H^U	Share of HRI sector waste that will be upcycled.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
A_H	Production cost shift parameter of the HRI sector.	1.986	0.376	0.342	0.113	Calibrated.
ε_H	Parameter that is used to indicate the production cost elasticity of the HRI sector.	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	Assumed.
α_H	The edible food waste rate of the HRI sector during preparation of the meal.	0.019	0.099	0.117	0.009	WRAP, 2011a , 2013b, 2013c, 2013d, 2013e,
$\bar{\alpha}_H$	The inedible food waste rate of the HRI sector during preparation of the meal.	0.013	0.099	0	0	2013f; assumed.
δ_H	Used rate of food by the HRI sector during preparation of the meal.	0.968	0.802	0.883	0.991	$= 1 - \alpha_H - \bar{\alpha}_H$

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
θ_H	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food waste reductions on the edible food loss abatement cost of the HRI sector during preparation of the meal.	76.923	10.101	1000	1000	Assumed.
E_H	Food waste abatement cost shift parameter for the HRI sector during preparation of the meal.	0.001	0.023	0.022	0.00005	Calibrated.
τ_H	Negative food waste abatement scale elasticity of the HRI sector during preparation of the meal.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Assumed.
α_A	The edible food waste rate of the consumer away from home.	0.278	0.051	0.060	0.005	WRAP, 2011a , 2013b, 2013c, 2013d, 2013e, 2013f; assumed.
$\bar{\alpha}_A$	The inedible food waste rate of the consumer away from home.	0.098	0.051	0	0	
δ_A	Used rate of food by the consumer away from home.	0.624	0.898	0.940	0.995	$=1 - \alpha_A - \bar{\alpha}_A$
θ_A	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food waste reductions on the edible food loss abatement cost of the consumer away from home.	10.204	19.608	1000	1000	Assumed.
E_A	Food waste abatement cost shift parameter for the consumer away from home.	0.008	0.0003	0.0004	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	Calibrated.
τ_A	Negative food waste abatement scale elasticity of the consumer away from home.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Assumed.

Table A6. Baseline data for the consumer's model

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
U	Utility of the consumer.	5.617	6.019	17.547	4.702	Result of calibration.
q_U	The quantity of food purchased from the retailer by the consumer.	1.074	3.471	7.847	11.421	DEFRA and ONS, 2017.
D	Food donations to the consumer.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
μ	The rate that food donations are truly additional.	1	1	1	1	Assumed.
q_C	Food consumption by the consumer at home.	0.663	2.176	5.556	10.382	$= q_U \cdot \delta_C$
q_A	Food consumption by the consumer away from home.	0.378	0.558	2.623	0.847	$= q_U \cdot \delta_A$
P_U	Price of food for the consumer at home.	4.483	2.124	2.102	0.601	DEFRA and ONS, 2017.
P_A	Price of food for the consumer away from home.	4.931	2.726	2.306	0.661	Assumed.
ϕ_C	Parameter that indicates intrinsic value of food consumption at home for the consumer.	20.223	8.371	8.181	1.562	Calibrated.
ϕ_A	Parameter that indicates intrinsic value of food consumption away from home for the consumer.	16.196	6.459	5.455	1.420	Calibrated.
λ_C	Parameter that indicates how fast utility of food consumption at home decreases for the consumer when the consumption at home increases.	16.406	1.913	0.669	0.078	Calibrated.
λ_A	Parameter that indicates how fast utility of food consumption away from home decreases for the consumer when the consumption away from home increases.	20.546	5.351	0.933	0.770	Calibrated.

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
κ	Parameter that indicates the rate of substitution between consumption at home and away from home for the consumer.	0.8	0.2	0.1	0.01	Calibrated.
α_c	Edible waste rate of food consumed at home.	0.153	0.122	0.292	0.091	WRAP, 2008, 2009, 2011b, 2013a, 2014, 2018b.
$\bar{\alpha}_c$	Inedible waste rate of food consumed at home.	0.229	0.251	0	0	WRAP, 2018b; assumed.
δ_c	Consumed rate of food at home.	0.618	0.627	0.708	0.909	$=1 - \alpha_c - \bar{\alpha}_c$
θ_A	Parameter that can change the effect of inedible food waste reductions on the edible food waste abatement cost of the consumer at home.	4.367	3.984	1000	1000	Assumed.
τ_c	Negative scale elasticity of food waste abatement at home.	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	-0.95	Calibrated.
E_c	Food waste abatement cost shift parameter for the consumer at home.	0.215	0.066	0.407	0.008	Calibrated.

Table A7. Baseline data for the dispositions

Symbol	Explanation	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk	Source
s	Price of a unit of food waste for the upcycler. This price could also be negative, which means that the upcycler receives money for processing the food waste.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
w	Price that supply chain actors pay to dispose of an unit of food waste.	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	Based on WRAP, 2012, 2017b, 2018c.
R	The quantity of food waste that is recycled.	0.308	0.505	1.930	0.868	Based on WRAP, 2012, 2017b, 2018c.
K_R	Supply shift parameter of food waste recycling.	0.387	0.635	2.429	1.093	Calibrated.
σ_R	Shape parameter for the FLW recovery production function.	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	Assumed.
D	The quantity of food waste that is donated.	0	0	0	0	Assumed.
K_D	Supply shift parameter of food donation.	0	0	0	0	Calibrated.
σ_D	Shape parameter for the donation function.	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	Assumed.
L	The quantity of food waste that is landfilled or incinerated.	0.885	1.633	3.258	2.051	Based on WRAP, 2012, 2017b, 2018c.
K_L	Supply shift parameter of food waste that is landfilled.	1.776	3.259	6.500	4.092	Calibrated.
σ_L	Shape parameter for the FLW landfill and incineration production function.	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	Assumed.

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11. Annex IV: The effects of voluntary reduction of FLW on the supply chain.

This Annex describes the results of the voluntary FLW reduction targets (see Tables 3 and 5) for 2030 in P1 and P3 across the supply chain. The voluntary targets of P1 and P3 are simulated on top of the mandatory targets described in section 5, such that the combination of both achieves the total FLW reduction target. For example, the mandatory target for the consumer in P 1 is to reduce its food waste by 30%. The voluntary target aims to reduce the consumer's food waste by another 20%-points compared to the baseline, such that the combination of both result in a 50% reduction in consumer's food waste.

It is important to note that a voluntary agreement to FLW reduction targets is debatable from an economic point of view. It implies that a supply chain actor would voluntarily accept lower profits because he must incur higher abatement costs. Therefore, we model the voluntary FLW reduction targets comparable to MAGNET's simulations of the voluntary targets. We assume that an agreement to the voluntary targets implies an investment in the development of new FLW reduction technologies . This lowers the abatement costs such that the actor can achieve the voluntary FLW reduction target, while the profit increases. A voluntary FLW reduction target for the consumer at home implies that public investments must be made to develop new food waste reducing technologies for the consumer at home. Note that this model does not capture any investment costs that a supply chain actor incurs.

The extent to which the abatement cost must be reduced to achieve the voluntary targets gives an indication of how likely it is to reach the target. The more the abatement costs must be decreased, the less likely it is that the voluntary target can be achieved. For example, a small adaptation to a current technology is easier to achieve but is also expected to decrease the abatement costs only slightly. A large exogenous decrease in the abatement costs can only be achieved with an extremely innovative development, which is much more difficult to develop.

Tables A8 – A13 show the results of the simulations relative to the baseline for the voluntary targets on top of the mandatory results that are explained in section 5. To isolate the effects of the voluntary reductions, we should compare these results to the results in section 5. The results of the simulations show that the abatement costs require a sharp decrease (Table A8) to approach the voluntary targets of P1 and P3 in 2030. The voluntary targets of these policy pathways cannot be achieved for chicken and fruit (as is indicated by the red cells in Table A9).

To explain why these voluntary targets cannot be achieved, we use the commodity fruit in P1 as an example. Even when edible FLW abatement becomes almost free of costs (-99.9%), the consumer reduces his quantity of generated fruit waste at home only by 32.7%. The reason behind this, is the effect of inedible food waste. The edible fruit waste rate decreases by 97.3% (Table A10), but the reduction in the abatement costs also causes

fruit consumption at home to become less expensive. This increases the demand for fruit at home from -24.5% of the mandatory target (Table 11) to -1.4% for the voluntary target compared to the baseline (Table A11). An increase in the demand for fruit at home results in a larger quantity of inedible waste, such that the reduction target cannot be reached. The voluntary reduction targets for the commodities without any inedible FLW at home were feasible to simulate with the model.

The substitution between FAH and FAFH in the simulations of the mandatory targets is also (partly) offset because the abatement costs for FAH decrease for the voluntary reduction targets. The HRI sector sold more food in the simulations of the mandatory targets for P1 and P3 compared to the baseline. When the abatement costs of FAH decrease, and the consumer substitutes back to eating more food at home because the consumption of FAH becomes less expensive, the HRI sales decrease. HRI sales decrease up to 10 percentage points in the simulations for the voluntary targets compared to the sales in the simulations of the mandatory targets in P1 for fruit and bread. The consumption FAH increases up to 42.7% for bread in P3.

Furthermore, the results from the voluntary targets show that the supply chain stages without any FLW reduction target increase their quantity of FLW further compared to the mandatory targets. The food waste generated by the consumption of FAFH even (more than) doubles for bread and milk in both policy pathways compared to the baseline (Table A9). The total quantity of generated FLW across the entire supply chain decreases further because of the voluntary reduction targets. This lowers the demand for FLW disposal services such that disposal costs decrease and the quantity of FLW of the stages without a reduction target increase.

The simulations of the voluntary agreements also underline the diverse effect that FLW reductions can have on the prices (Table A12) as explained in section 5. The simulations of the mandatory FLW reduction targets showed that all prices decreased in P1 and P3, except for the retailer's price of bread in P3 (Table 12). All prices in P1 still decrease compared to the baseline when the voluntary targets are added to the simulations. However, the voluntary targets increase the prices compared to the mandatory targets, which results in a smaller overall price decrease for both policy pathways. Some prices increase so fast for the voluntary targets in P3 that the initial reduction in the mandatory target is completely offset, and the prices increase compared to the baseline. All prices of milk along the supply chain, except for the retailer, are expected to increase. The processor's (+13.2%) and retailer's (+9.3%) price of chicken will also increase compared to the baseline because of the voluntary targets in P3.

Table A13 shows the absolute changes in FLW abatement costs because of the voluntary agreement. This table indicates how much a supply chain stage will save on FLW abatement efforts because of the development of new food-saving technologies. The largest savings are expected for the consumer of FAH. Some supply chain stages experience an increase in the abatement costs, for example, the farmer and THS in P1. These stages sell more food compared to the mandatory policy which increases their abatement costs. Moreover, the largest reductions in absolute abatement costs

compared to the mandatory targets are expected in P3. This can be explained by the fact that this policy pathway relies the most on the voluntary agreements. A larger part of the aimed for reduction in P1 is already achieved by the disposal taxes, while these disposal taxes have a much smaller role in P3.

The results of the voluntary targets emphasise the conclusions of the main text in section 6 of this deliverable. First, a large decrease in the abatement costs is necessary to approximate the voluntary FLW reduction targets. Second, the simulations of the voluntary targets highlight the importance of inedible FLW on the extent to which total FLW can be reduced. Third, the supply chain stages without a FLW reduction target further increase their FLW when other stages comply to a voluntary agreement.

Table A8: Required % shift of the abatement costs for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030.

Required % shift of the abatement costs of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	0	0	0	0
THS	0	0	0	0
Processor	-65.0	-69.8	-72.3	-32.7
Retailer	-66.6	-67.8	-69.0	-53.5
HRI	0	0	0	0
Consumer	-99.9	-99.9	-77.5	-57.0
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-29.5	-36.0	-47.7	-34.6
THS	0	0	0	0
Processor	-99.9	-99.9	-99.9	-79.2
Retailer	-99.9	-99.9	-83.9	-72.5
HRI	0	0	0	0
Consumer	-99.9	-99.9	-83.9	-72.5

Table A9: Changes in the total quantity of FLW for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030.

% Change in the quantity of FLW of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer pre-harvest	7.1	-0.1	0.1	5.4
Farmer post-harvest	9.2	1.7	20.2	14.0
THS	8.4	0.7	19.3	12.9
Processor	-25.0	-25.0	-25.0	-24.9
Retail	-50.0	-50.0	-50.0	-50.1
HRI	5.9	5.4	-0.2	12.9
FAFH	36.6	47.9	127.6	99.8
FAH	-40.5	-32.7	-50.0	-50.1
Retail + FAH	-42.2	-35.6	-50.0	-50.1
Total post-harvest supply chain	-17.4	-27.0	-31.6	-26.8
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer pre-harvest	3.2	0.4	-0.3	-6.2
Farmer post-harvest	-10.0	-10.1	-10.1	-10.0
THS	7.4	15.4	24.2	11.1
Processor	-49.6	-48.7	-49.9	-50.0
Retail	-97.0	-96.8	-58.7	-52.5
HRI	5.4	3.0	-2.6	4.8
FAFH	51.4	53.3	153.8	121.6
FAH	-32.9	-23.2	-45.2	-48.3
Retail + FAH	-44.3	-35.6	-50.1	-50.0
Total post-harvest supply chain	-24.0	-30.1	-35.3	-31.7

Note: Red-shaded cells indicate a policy objective was not achieved in the simulations. Green-shaded cells indicate that the policy objective was achieved in the simulation.

Table A10: Changes in edible FLW rates for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030.

% Change in the edible FLW rate of	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Post-harvest farmer	12.3	4.7	22.1	15.0
THS	12.2	4.5	21.7	14.3
Processor	-43.8	-42.1	-44.6	-23.3
Retailer	-46.8	-47.6	-49.9	-48.9
HRI	7.7	4.5	4.5	9.5
Consumer FAFH	47.5	88.5	139.8	94.2
Consumer FAH	-97.2	-97.3	-53.7	-50.5
Policy pathway 3				
Post-harvest farmer	-9.0	-17.4	-10.6	-10.9
THS	8.3	3.1	23.2	9.7
Processor	-96.1	-96.7	-96.5	-50.6
Retailer	-97.1	-97.1	-61.2	-53.3
HRI	13.7	4.6	4.8	7.0
Consumer FAFH	75.6	106.2	175.1	126.6
Consumer FAH	-96.4	-96.6	-53.2	-50.9

Table A11: Changes in sold and consumed quantities for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030.

% Change in sales and consumption of	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	-3.3	-3.7	-2.0	-1.3
THS	-3.4	-3.9	-2.3	-1.9
Processor	2.9	-3.4	-1.2	-1.9
Retailer	-2.6	-1.4	8.0	0.8
HRI	1.1	2.5	-5.1	3.0
Consumer FAFH	-20.3	-2.7	-13.6	2.5
Consumer FAH	20.9	17.3	31.9	5.9
Total consumption of food	6.0	13.3	17.3	5.6
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-0.8	11.9	0.8	1.3
THS	-0.9	11.8	0.5	0.9
Processor	13.2	3.9	3.1	1.5
Retailer	9.3	12.3	17.0	5.3
HRI	-2.8	0.1	-7.7	-2.1
Consumer FAFH	-35.6	-5.9	-18.1	-2.7
Consumer FAH	35.3	33.4	42.7	10.6
Total consumption of food	9.7	25.3	23.2	9.6

Note: total consumption of food is FAH + FAFH.

Table A12: Changes in sale prices for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030.

% Change in price of	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	-17.6	-3.2	-2.4	-6.9
THS	-17.0	-3.1	-1.8	-6.1
Processor	-12.4	-5.7	-2.8	-5.3
Retail	-10.6	-8.9	-7.4	-5.3
HRI	-6.6	-4.9	-3.2	-3.8
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-0.8	-0.6	-2.5	4.8
THS	-0.9	-0.1	-0.9	2.7
Processor	13.2	-5.5	-2.8	1.1
Retail	9.3	-15.1	-10.3	-4.1
HRI	-2.8	-5.0	-3.8	0.4

Table A13: Absolute change in abatement costs between the mandatory and voluntary target for the targeted supply chain stages (in billion £).

Absolute change in abatement costs	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	0.010	0.017	0.004	0.006
THS	0.003	0.005	0.003	0.009
Processor	-0.097	-0.052	-0.074	-0.011
Retailer	-0.06	-0.105	-0.542	-0.168
HRI (total)*	-0.005	-0.011	-0.051	-0.005
Consumer	-1.264	-1.484	-2.919	-0.333
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-0.012	-0.002	-0.02	-0.027
THS	0	0.006	-0.003	0.001
Processor	-0.261	-0.178	-0.185	-0.036
Retailer	-0.261	-0.482	-1.011	-0.241
HRI (total)*	-0.012	-0.011	-0.066	-0.005
Consumer FAH	-1.216	-1.477	-3.714	-0.415

*The HRI pays for the food waste abatement during the preparation of the food and for the consumer of FAFH

PART II

Analysis of the Impact of Zero food waste Scenarios: a MAGNET analysis

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1. Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
FAH	Food At Home
FAFH	Food Away From Home
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
MAGNET	Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool
P1	Policy pathway 1
P2	Policy pathway 2
P3	Policy pathway 3
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
FSC	Food supply chain
EU27	European Union
BAU	Business-as-usual scenario
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GDP	Gross domestic product

1. The impact of FLW reduction pathways on FLW magnitude and composition

FLW reduction scenarios

The investigated scenarios are compared with our business-as-usual (BaU) baseline scenario which builds on key drivers such as population and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth defined in line with the shared socioeconomic pathway 2 (SSP2) of the United Nations (IIASA, 2024). The model database is the Global Trade Analysis (GTAP) database version 11 (Aguilar et al., 2023).

In Pathway 1 (P1) Food Loss and Waste (FLW) is reduced by 0% for primary production (post-harvest handling & storage), 10% for manufacturing, and 30% for distribution and retail and final consumers. The mandatory reduction is achieved by implementing an endogenous tax on FLW generation in each of the different stages. Additionally, a voluntary target of 25% FLW reduction for manufacturing and 50% reduction for distribution and retail and final consumers is modelled by a technological change in FLW generation mimicking an option where the same amount of consumption lead to less FLW without any further cost. The term “technological change” resembles a preference shift of consumers towards commodities generating less FLW, which in turn leads to a lower amount of FLW for the same amount of food consumed.

In Pathway 2 (P2) FLW is reduced by 50% in 2030 and near 100% in 2050 in all stages of the supply chain. These changes are implemented with a stand-alone endogenous tax on FLW generation equally applied across all stages of the food supply chain. Finally, in Pathway 3 (P3) mandatory and voluntary targets are applied. A 15% food waste reduction target by distribution and retail and consumers is achieved with an endogenous tax. Additionally, a 50% reduction in FLW by 2030 and near 100% reduction by 2050 is reached by a voluntary target, modelled as a technology change in waste generation. An overview of the investigated scenarios is provided in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Overview of the magnitude of FLW reduction policies across investigated scenarios in 2030 and 2050

Scenario	FLW reduction Pathway 1				FLW reduction Pathway 2				FLW reduction Pathway 3				
	Type of measure	Voluntary reduction	Mandatory reduction		Voluntary reduction	Mandatory reduction		Voluntary reduction	Mandatory reduction				
Target year		2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050

Post-harvest Handling & Storage	-	-	50%	90%	50%	100%	-	-
Processing and Manufacturing	25%	10%	50%	90%	50%	100%		
Distribution & Retail (incl. transportation)	50%	30%	50%	90%	50%	100%	15%	15%
Consumption	50%	30%	50%	90%	50%	100%	15%	15%
Average magnitude of levied FLW generation tax in the EU27		14%	25%	114%		0%		

FLW Magnitude

In the BAU scenario, FLW are projected to decrease by 4,309 million tons (-8.7%) from 2030 to 2050, although specific countries stand-out, experiencing a rise (figure 1). The reduction of FLW is driven by two key changes in consumption patterns. First, a small shift toward animal-based product consumption as incomes rise leads to reduced FLW levels by 2050 in the EU27, as animal-based products generally present lower FLW rates compared to plant-based products. Second, as incomes rise particularly in southern and eastern European countries, consumption shifts towards food services, decreasing food consumed at home (FAH). As waste margins in Distribution & Retail are lower than home consumption, preference shifts towards food services (Food Away From Home – FAFH) lead to a decrease in food waste generation (figure 2).

Change in Food loss and waste generation across EU27 countries in Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario

Figure 1. Change (%) in FLW generation in the EU27 in the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario from 2017 to 2030 and from 2030 to 2050. [Green (red) color means a reduction (an increase) in FLW]

Change (%) in food loss and waste generation from 2019 to 2050 in the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario

Figure 2. Change (% of kg of FLW per person) in FLW generation across food supply chain stages from 2019 to 2050 in the EU27 in the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario.

In P1, the introduction of a direct taxation on FLW at different stages of the supply chain coupled with agents' voluntary reductions of FLW at Manufacturing, Distribution & Retail, and Consumption results in a cumulative decrease in FLW of around 31,277 Ktons (-62.1%) in 2030 (figure 3). Across stages, major absolute reductions are observed at Consumption (household) level, where FLW decreases by 21,274 Ktons (-80%) in 2030. Imposing stand-alone taxes on FLW generation (P2) has a more moderate impact on reducing FLW than when taxes are combined with voluntary reduction efforts (P1). In 2030, applying equal taxes across all stages of the food supply chain (FSC) mainly reduces consumption-level FLW by 13,273 Ktons (-49.8%) compared to the BAU scenario. However, this reduction is results lower than that achieved in P1, where combined measures reduce FLW by an additional 8,001 Ktons (-37.8%) relative to P2. Raising taxes by 2050 enables an additional reduction in FLW generation of 20,535 Ktons compared to 2030, achieving a total reduction of 41,671 Ktons (-90.1% at each stage of the food supply chain) relative to the BAU scenario by 2050 (figure 3).

Voluntary reductions in FLW generation across FSC stages have a similar impact on FLW reduction compared to FLW taxes, although their effects on the broader economy differ. In 2030, a voluntary reduction of FLW by 50% cumulatively decreases lost and discarded foods by 25,324 Ktons, with around half of this reduction observed at Consumption stage (-13,257 Ktons compared to BAU). Similarly, when voluntary reductions are increased to reach a FLW reduction close to 100%, household FLW have the largest decrease in absolute terms (-23,482 Ktons) compared to BAU in 2050.

Figure 3. Change (Ktons and percentage) in FLW generation in the EU27 by supply chain stages and scenarios and with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario in 2030 and 2050.

FLW Composition

Across scenarios, as FLW reduction targets are equally imposed across food commodities, absolute reductions are highest for plant-based products, which, on average, present the largest magnitudes of FLW and result majorly impacted when reduction measures are introduced. From figure 4 is possible to observe that FLW from horticulture present the largest absolute decrease across food commodities, followed by FLW generated from cereals and meat. In P1, horticulture FLW decreases by 15,727 Ktons (-60.4%) accounting for around 50% of the total FLW reduction in the EU27 (figure 4). Similarly, when stand-alone taxes on FLW are introduced, reductions in FLW are highest for horticulture (from -12,930 in 2030 to a -21,116 in 2050 with respect to BAU) and cereals (from -3,150 in 2030 to a -5,179 in 2050 with respect to BAU).

While a parallel trend across commodities is simultaneously observed in case of voluntary FLW reductions (P3, figure 4), the imposition of taxes results in moderately stronger decrease of animal-based FLW from meat, dairy and fish, compared to the case of voluntary FLW reductions (around 83 Ktons in 2030). This is due to the income effect generated by the taxes in P2 which contained the demand for animal-food products (figure 11) compared to P3, resulting in a lower generation of FLW.

Finally, a major reduction across scenarios is additionally observed for FLW from oil seeds, which decrease from around 1000 Ktons in the case of stand-alone taxes or voluntary reductions in 2030, to around 1800 Ktons in case of stand-alone voluntary reductions (P3) in 2050. In P1, the application of both reduction instruments in 2030 has stronger effects than stand-alone interventions, resulting in an additional reduction in oilseed FLW of 361 Ktons compared to P2, and 291 Ktons compared to P3.

Figure 4. Change (Ktons) of FLW generation in the EU27 by food commodity across investigated scenarios in 2030 and 2050.

2. The impact of FLW reduction pathways on producers

Production and prices

Implementing FLW reduction measures, whether through direct taxes or voluntary choices by producers and consumers, improves production efficiency by reducing the amount of food lost throughout the supply chain. As FLW decreases, producers can achieve the same output with less waste, effectively lowering production costs. This efficiency gain translates into a higher total output, increasing overall food production and supply in the EU27 (figure 5). With greater supply levels, average producer prices for food commodities tend to moderately decline across the investigated scenarios (figures 6 and 7), with price reductions being largely driven by the balance between the improved efficiency and the broader availability of food products.

Across FLW reduction strategies, taxes on FLW generation result in a smaller decrease in producer food prices compared to voluntary reductions. When taxes are imposed at production stages—such as Post-Harvest Handling & Storage, Manufacturing, and

Distribution & Retail—they introduce additional costs that moderately increase the prices of food commodities. This added cost tempers the reduction in producer prices because the burden of the tax partially offsets the price drop linked to the efficiency gains from reduced FLW. In contrast, scenarios where FLW reductions are achieved voluntarily—with no additional tax burden—allow production efficiency to improve without these cost increases, leading to a more substantial drop in producer prices (figure 6). A comparison of P2 and 3 reveals a slight difference in average food price reductions for producers. In 2030, producer prices decrease by 0.2% in P2, slightly less than the 0.3% reduction observed in Pathway 3. By 2050, the effects are more pronounced: prices drop by 0.3% in P2, compared to a larger decrease of 0.5% in P3.

Changes in producer prices are directly tied to production levels, with larger reductions in producer prices generally leading to greater increases in production volumes (see figure 5). In P3, voluntary reductions result in a greater rise in food production across the EU27 (average 0.4% in 2030 and 1.0% in 2050) compared to P2 (average 0.3% in 2030 and 0.8% in 2050) where a higher tax level lead to a smaller relative increase in total production. The combination of both interventions in P1 leads to stronger FLW reductions with respect to P2 and P3, parallely resulting in the highest increase in production (average 0.7%) across scenarios in 2030.

Across food commodities, the impact on prices is strongest for those that are more FLW-intensive and thus more sensitive to FLW reduction efforts. Producer prices for cereals, grains, and horticultural products see the most substantial declines (figure 7). Specifically, producer prices for cereals and grains drop by 0.7% in Pathway 2 in 2030, reaching up to a 2.5% decrease in P3 by 2050, with average production in the EU27 increasing by up to 0.5% in the same scenario. Likewise, horticultural commodities—such as fruits, vegetables, roots, tubers, and pulses—experience price reductions from 0.06% in P2 in 2030 to 2.1% in P3 by 2050, accompanied by a notable 3.5% increase in production in 2050 under P3.

Heterogenous price changes across food commodities result in different impacts across EU27 countries. Southern EU27 countries, such as Italy, Portugal, and Greece, along with eastern EU27 countries like the

Czech Republic and Estonia, where cereals, grains and horticulture represent more than half of total agrifood production experience the most significant reductions in producer prices across EU27 regions, parallely seeing the largest increases in production across the different scenarios. Differently, countries with higher production of commodities presenting lower FLW rates (e.g. meats and sugars) experience a more moderate

increase in production, as production prices for such commodities decrease comparatively less across scenarios.

Figure 5. Change (%) in Ktons of food produced in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050. (The darker the color, the higher the increase in food production)

Figure 6. Change (%) in producer prices of consumer food products in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Figure 7. Change (%) in producer food prices across scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Land demand

Increases in food production directly impact the use of agricultural land in the EU27, raising demand and prices across countries in both 2030 and 2050 (figure 8). Although production changes for land-intensive animal-based products are relatively moderate, the overall rise in food production increases land use, with heightened demand leading to increased agricultural land prices across the EU27. On average, land demand in the EU27 in 2030 increases from 0.12% in P 2 up to 0.23% in P1, a trend that is further intensified in 2050 where average land demand increases up to 0.42% in P3. This leads to a higher appreciation of agricultural land in the EU27, with average prices rising from 0.6% in Pathway 2 to 0.9% in Pathway 1 by 2030, and further increasing to 1.0% in Pathway 3 by 2050 (figure 8).

Across countries, land appreciation effects are most pronounced in countries experiencing more significant increases in production and in countries where agricultural land is limited. Higher production levels result in agricultural land prices in Italy (from 1.5-2.9% in 2030 up to 2.8-3.4% in 2050), Portugal (from 0.8-1.8% in 2030 up to 2.2-2.7% in 2050) and Czech Republic (from 0.6-1.0% in 2030 up to 1.2-1.4% in 2050). Similarly, in land-scarce regions, although the increase in production is rather modest, the limited availability of land leads to a greater appreciation in land value. The highest increase is observed in The Netherlands where land price increase from 1.8% in P2 to 3.6% in P 1 in 2030 and further rise by 4.1% and 4.9% in P2 and P3, respectively, in 2050. Similar effects are additionally observed for Denmark where land appreciates especially in 2050, with a rise in price from 2.1% in P 2 to 2.3% in P 3 compared to BAU.

Figure 8. Change (%) in agricultural land price in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Wages

Rising production trends generate positive impacts on agricultural wages across the EU27, exerting a moderate increase in real wages across scenarios (figures 9 and 10). Although higher land prices increase average production costs for producers, the increasing volumes of agricultural production drive an increase in labour demand in agriculture across European regions. In 2030, this is more pronounced in P1 where a higher production increase drives EU27 average agricultural wages up by 0.4%, slightly more compared to P2 (0.2%) and P3 (0.23%). However, this average increase hides labour-specific trends as the rise in agricultural production has different impacts across labour types. Demand for labour particularly rises for unskilled labour, positively impacting average wages for unskilled agricultural workers, with increases from 0.27% in 2030 to 0.65% in 2050, especially in Pathway 3 (figure 9).

As changes in production differ by commodities, wage-related impacts vary across agricultural sectors (figure 10). Countries with a more unskilled labour-intensive horticultural sectors such as Italy or Spain primarily see a stronger increase in agricultural wages. Differently, countries that primary rely on labour and land in sectors that face a rather moderate production increase (e.g. meats, dairies, and oils), experience a more moderate increase in wages as higher land prices and a relatively contained increase in labour demand result contains the rise in unskilled wages. This is the case for Ireland or Lithuania, where average real agricultural unskilled wages increase relatively less across investigated scenarios. Finally, the rise in agricultural wages is more contained in countries with limited agricultural land and capital-intensive agricultural sectors, such as Denmark and The Netherlands, where real wages in agriculture increase relatively less due to higher land prices and a relatively lower increase in labour demand across scenarios.

Figure 9. Change (%) in real agricultural wages in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and

Figure 10. Change (%) in real agricultural wages in the EU27 by production sector across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline

3. The impact of FLW reduction pathways on consumers

Changes in food production and the decline in average food prices directly affect food consumption in the EU27, leading to a moderate increase across all scenarios compared to the BAU scenario in both 2030 and 2050 (figure 11).

As average producer prices decrease, consumers respond positively to the lower prices, leading to an increase in overall food demand across EU27 countries. In scenarios where taxes on FLW generation are imposed, the resulting increase in food demand is less pronounced compared to scenarios where FLW reductions are achieved through voluntary measures, as the tax burden affects consumers budgets limiting the rise in demand. In 2030, food consumption increases by an average 0.3% in P2 and by 0.4% in Pathway 3, a trend that is more pronounced in P1 where relatively stronger reductions in FLW and depreciations of food commodities lead to a 0.6% increase in food consumption. Similar effects are observed for 2050 where food demand further rises by 0.65% and 0.9% in P2 and P3, respectively.

Across EU27 countries, effects are relatively more pronounced in countries where FLW reductions lead to stronger increases in production, and average producer prices are lower (section 3). Food demand increases mainly in Italy (from 0.06-1.1% in 2030 to 1.2-1.6% in 2050) and Portugal (from 0.4-0.8% in 2030 to 1.0-1.3% in 2050), with the highest increase across EU27 countries observed in Portugal where food demand rises from 0.6-1.2% in 2030 to 1.5-1.9% in 2050 (figure 11).

In response to changing producer prices, final food demand majorly rises for plant-based commodities (figure 12), which, on average, see the largest depreciation in production prices when FLW decrease (section 3). Consumer demand principally rises for horticulture commodities (mainly root and tubers), increasing in 2030 by an average 1.4% in P2 and slightly more in in P3 (2.0%) where no taxes, hence budget constraints on final consumption, are imposed. Similarly, in P1 where stronger reductions on FLW are achieved mainly through voluntary choices, food demand for horticulture reaches the highest rise across scenarios in 2030, increasing by 2.9%. Similar demand trends are observed for cereals and grains, for which average EU27 final demand increases up to 2.9% in P1 in 2030, further rising by 3.4% and 4.4% in P2 and P3, respectively, in 2050 (figure 12).

Despite FLW reductions exert on average negative pressures on agricultural wages (section 3), producers food prices decrease relatively more, resulting in an increasing

final food demand as well as higher food purchasing power¹ and food affordability for consumers across the EU27 (figure 13). In 2030, tax-induced reductions (P2) result in a 0.15% increase in purchasing power, an estimate that rises to 0.23% when FLW is reduced voluntarily (Pathway 3). The combined implementation of both measures (P 1) results in an even greater increase, boosting purchasing power by 0.3%. Effects in 2050 are more pronounced as the average producer prices further decrease. In P2, purchasing powers in the EU27 increase by an average 0.32%, while in P3 the observed increase reaches an average 0.5% across EU27 countries. Regional effects are more pronounced in southern Europe, particularly Italy and Portugal, where price reductions are most significant (figure 6), and in eastern Europe where, despite a decline in wages, the even larger drop in producer prices enhances overall food affordability for consumers.

¹ Food purchasing power is calculated as change in food price/change in real wages.

Figure 11. Change (%) in food consumption in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050. (The darker the color, the higher increase in food consumption)

Change (%) in final consumer food demand across scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario

Figure 12. Change (%) in consumer demand of food commodities in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050

Change (%) in final consumer food purchasing power across scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario

Figure 13. Change (%) in consumer purchasing power of food commodities in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

4. The impact of FLW reduction pathways on trade

The rise in consumer purchasing power increases food demand, driving demand for imported foods while reducing exports, as more domestically produced foods are redirected to meet the higher demand within the EU27 (Figure 14). By 2030, the higher increase in food demand observed in P1 drives a stronger increase in food imports (average 0.24%) compared to P2 (average 0.15%) and P3 (average 0.17%). Imports primarily consist of roots, tubers, fruits, vegetables, and rice, sourced mainly from Africa and South and Central America. Similarly, in 2050, imports demand increases relatively more when voluntary reductions occur in comparison to tax-driven FLW reductions (figure 14), with Africa and South and Central America remaining the largest source of imported foods. Food exports decline in all scenarios with reductions being more pronounced in P2 where higher taxes moderate the drop in food prices, reducing foreign demand for EU27 products compared to P1 and P3, where EU27 food prices fall more steeply.

Figure 14. Change (million dollars) in magnitude of food trade (exports and imports) between the EU27 and the rest of the world across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Trade impacts across the EU27 vary by region, with overall trade volumes within the EU27 increasing as a result of FLW reduction policies (figure 15). This effect is particularly strong in P1 and P3, where lower tax burdens enable a more pronounced rise in final food demand, leading to greater import volumes. Food exports towards other

EU27 countries primarily increase in western Europe, particularly in The Netherlands (from 95 to 180 million dollars in 2030 and up to 180-240 million dollars in 2050), and in southern European countries, particularly Spain, where exports increase by 110-210 million dollars in 2030 and by 240-290 million tons in 2050. Positive effects on exports are parallelly observed in Denmark, France, Greece, and Bulgaria where due to a relatively lower increase in food imports, the balance of trade increases across scenarios (figure 15). Increases in food imports within the EU27 are stronger in southern Europe, mainly in Italy (from 90 to 120 million dollars in 2030 and up to 180-190 million dollars in 2050) and Portugal (from 30 to 50 million dollars in 2030 and up to 80-90 million dollars in 2050), and in western Europe, particularly in Germany, where the market volume of imported foods rises from 190 million tons in P2 up 330 million tons in P1 in 2030, and further increases by 360 million tons and 410 million tons in P2 and P3, respectively, in 2050.

Change (million dollars) in intra-EU27 food trade across scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario

Figure 15. Change (million dollars) in magnitude of intra-EU27 food trade (exports and imports) across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Trade-related effects directly influence GDP, as shifts in trade balances impact GDP levels (figure 16). Changes in imports and exports due to FLW reduction policies alter the trade surplus or deficit, leading to corresponding moderate adjustments in GDP, particularly as demand patterns and trade volumes evolve across different EU27 regions over time. In countries where exports rise more than imports, the resulting improvement

in the trade balance positively impacts GDP growth across the investigated scenarios (figure 16). This is the case for The Netherlands and Spain, where GDP moderately grows by 2030 and 2050, but also for Denmark, France, Greece, and Bulgaria, where higher exports positively affect GDP (figure 16). Differently, countries where increases in imports are more pronounced, experience a reduction in their balance with negative impacts on GDP. This is the case for Germany and Italy, where an average decrease in GDP is observed across scenarios in both 2030 and 2050 (figure 16).

Figure 16. Change (%) in gross domestic product (GDP) in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

5. The impact of FLW reduction pathways on the environment

Greenhouse gas emissions

Reducing FLW in the EU27 exerts positive effects on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, decreasing magnitudes across scenarios in both 2030 and 2050 (figure 17). Notably, FLW reduction policies lead to substantial emission decreases in waste treatment and waste collection, particularly in P1 by 2030, where emissions drop by nearly 7 million tons of CO₂-equivalents. Effects in 2050 are more pronounced, with the achieved reduction in P3 reaching nearly 11 million tons of CO₂-eq, a decrease that is more substantial compared to P2 where GHG emission decrease by around 9 million tons of CO₂-eq.

However, emissions across scenarios increase in primary agriculture, due to a higher production and use of chemical fertilisers (figure 19), and in non-food sectors, following the rise in non-food demand linked to lower food prices and higher food affordability driven by FLW reductions (figure 17). In P1, total GHG emissions from primary agriculture increase by 1.5 million tons of CO₂-eq, relatively more than in P2 and P3, where emission rise by 0.9 million tons of CO₂-eq and 0.8 million tons of CO₂-eq, respectively. In 2050, emissions from primary agriculture in P2 increase by 2.1 million tons of CO₂-eq, higher than the rise observed in P3 (1.9 million tons of CO₂-eq).

Similarly, emissions from non-food sectors in 2030 rise from 1 million tons of CO₂-eq in P2 up to 1.5 million tons of CO₂-eq in P1 where the combination of voluntary reductions and taxes yields comparatively higher effects on rising non-food demand. In 2050, the rise in non-food emissions is relatively more contained in P2 (1.7 million tons of CO₂-eq), where taxes affect consumer budgets limiting the rise in non-food demand, compared to P3 where voluntary reductions generate an increase of non-food emission of 2.1 million tons of CO₂-eq in the EU27. Non-food emissions primarily increase from textiles, manufacturing, and energy sectors, which cumulatively account for around 80% of the increased emissions from non-food sectors in 2050.

In the EU27 regions, the reduction in GHG emissions from waste treatment exceeds the increases seen in non-food and agricultural sectors. However, in countries which mostly rely on incineration as the preferred way of final disposal of waste as opposed to landfilling, total emissions are rising. Most GHG emissions result from landfilling, whereas incineration and, to a lesser extent, composting also contribute to emissions—but at a lower intensity compared to landfilling.. Therefore, the growing emissions from agricultural production and non-food sectors are not offset by the reductions achieved in

waste treatment in countries which mostly incinerate and compost food waste, leading to an overall increase in total emissions (see Figure 18). This is the case for The Netherlands, Belgium, Luxemburg, and Sweden where higher agriculture-related emissions outweigh the reductions observed in waste treatment sectors, and Austria and Germany, where rising emissions from non-food sectors contribute to an overall increase in emissions across all scenarios by 2030 and 2050.

Figure 17. Change (million tons of CO₂-equivalents) in greenhouse gas emissions by source in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Figure 18. Change (million tons of CO₂-equivalents) in greenhouse gas emissions by country in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Fertilisers use

The observed rise in agricultural production and land use (Section 3) has direct effect on the demand and use of chemical fertilisers (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) in the EU27, increasing their use compared to the BAU scenario in both 2030 and 2050 (figure 19). In 2030, average Nitrogen (N) applications in the EU27 show the highest increase in P1 (+1.18%), mainly due to greater reductions in food losses for cereals and grains, which boost the production of these crops compared to the two other Pathways. Similar trends are observed for Phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K), which simultaneously increase by 1.16% in P1, more than in P2 and P3, where average chemical fertiliser use rises by 0.73% and 0.80%, respectively. In 2050, the more substantial agrifood production growth and consequent increase in land demand in P3 drive a higher fertiliser demand across the EU27 (+2.09%) also in comparison to P2, where total fertiliser use rises more moderately, with an average increase of 1.76%.

Figure 19. Change (%) in chemical fertilisers use (N, P, K) for agricultural production in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

6. Conclusions

Voluntary reductions of FLW as well as direct taxes on FLW generation at various stages of the food supply chain, are effective measures of reducing lost and wasted foods across EU27 food supply chains (FSCs).

To achieve a 50% reduction in FLW by 2030 via taxation (P2), a 25% tax on FLW generation would need to be applied uniformly across all stages of the FSC, impacting both producers and consumers. Meeting even more ambitious FLW reduction targets, such as a 90% reduction by 2050, would necessitate substantially higher taxes—potentially reaching 110%—to drive the desired behavioural and operational changes. While the burden of taxation may affect producers and consumers, the effects on the broader economy are rather moderate also in comparison to a counterfactual scenario where FLW reductions are achieved mainly through voluntary choices of agents (P1 and P3). While voluntary reductions in FLW may be preferable as they avoid imposing direct costs on agents along the FSC, the choice between direct taxation and promoting positive behavioral changes depends on how each of these two measures generates socioeconomic and environmental synergies and spillovers in 2050.

From a FLW perspective, both instruments are effective in reducing FLW. In the EU27, Distribution & Retail and Consumption stages represent the major hotspot for FLW generation and should be prioritised by policy interventions in order to achieve a more significant reduction in FLW in 2030 and 2050. In this, plant-based commodities—particularly cereals, grains, and horticultural products—account for the largest share of FLW in the EU27. Consequently, these commodities should be targeted with priority policies, as reductions here would yield the most substantial overall FLW decrease compared to other food categories.

Regardless of the specific instrument used to reduce FLW, several unintended spillover effects emerge from reduction policies, potentially offsetting the anticipated benefits of FLW interventions.

First, economic spillovers into food production increase land demand, use, and prices in 2030 and 2050. The increasing production efficiency achieved through lower amounts of food lost during production processes leads to a rise in agrifood production especially for cereals, grains, and horticulture, commodities that are by definition FLW-intensive and primarily benefit from FLW reductions. While the increase in agrifood supply across EU27 countries has simultaneous benefits on consumers by lowering producers' prices and expanding final food demand, the expanded food production drives parallel demand for key production inputs, including land. The rising use of agricultural land is a key driver for environmental impacts (Maxwell et al., 2016) and has negative consequences on several ecosystem services (Power, 2010), including loss of biodiversity (Leclere et al., 2020). Across FLW reduction instruments, the imposition of taxes leads to a lower magnitude of economic spillovers. This is because reductions in production prices are relatively more moderate due to the additional costs generated by the taxes in comparison to voluntary shifts where no additional costs are generated. The lower reduction in producer prices limits the increase in production, simultaneously leading to a more moderate increase in land use under stand-alone FLW taxation policies.

However, positive social spillovers are found in a moderate average increase in wages for workers in agriculture. While the observed increase in production generates negative effects on land use and prices, higher production volumes generate upward pressures on average agricultural wages across the EU27, as labour demand increases across scenarios in both 2030 and 2050. Unskilled workers majorly benefit compared to skilled workers given the higher increase in unskilled labour demand across EU27 agrifood sectors. This mainly benefits countries that largely rely on unskilled workers in agricultural sectors, helping reduce the wage gap between skilled and unskilled labour by 2050. Major benefits are achieved by countries with labour-intensive horticultural sectors, where production expansion boosts labour demand and has stronger effects on

raising agricultural wages. However, in countries with capital-intensive agricultural sectors wages rise moderately less in response to the rise in production. Similarly, as the rise in labour demand mainly concerns cereals, grains, and horticultural sectors, in regions where the production of other products represent the largest share in agriculture, wages expand relatively less as labour demand grows more moderately. In line with the observed changes in production, the increase in average wages in agriculture is more contained when stand-alone taxes on FLW are imposed in comparison with scenarios where voluntary reductions are imposed.

Lastly, environmental spillovers are found in the increased emissions from non-food sectors and agricultural sectors respectively driven by a higher non-food demand and use of chemical fertilisers. Reducing FLW in the EU27 yields significant benefits for GHG emissions, reducing waste treatment and waste collection emissions, demonstrating the effectiveness of FLW policies in creating synergies for tackling economy-wide GHG emissions. However, achieved benefits are countered by increasing emissions in primary agriculture and non-food sectors, particularly in countries where incomes are higher and agricultural practices are input intensive. The rise in agricultural emissions—driven by increased production and the use of chemical fertilisers—highlights the urgent need to shift towards more sustainable agricultural practices in order to bend the curve of rising emissions when food production in EU27 increases. With this, the higher demand for non-food commodities linked to a lower consumer spending on food products exacerbates emissions from non-food sectors, on average presenting higher emission factors compared to food sectors. This underscores the potential generation of rebound effects in other emissions-intensive activities, emphasising the need for accounting for non-food related impacts when policies targeting the food system are applied.

Tackling spillover effects is crucial for devising policy measures that are capable of minimising arising unintended negative effects. Taxes on FLW generation prove to be more effective in containing spillovers compared to stand-alone voluntary reductions. Despite the introduction of direct taxations may result in additional economic burdens for agents across the EU27 FSC, the moderate negative effects observed in the presence of a large tax (around 110%) that allows to reduce FLW by 90% indicate that such measures may represent a more effective way to reduce FLW while containing spillovers. Typically, price-based mechanisms tend to be more effective at promoting sustainable behaviours and reducing FLW than “soft” measures, such as awareness campaigns or educational programs that rely on voluntary behavioural changes (Latka et al., 2021; Katare et al., 2017; Hamilton et al., 2019). In the EU27, as consumers spend a limited share of their budget on food products and face a rather low elasticity of demand (i.e. demand does not change considerably when food prices change) (Grodzicki &

Jankiewicz, 2022), applying high taxes on FLW does not significantly disrupt consumption patterns, suggesting that monetary interventions are unlikely to pose risks to food security. However, as incomes are likely to be impacted through changes in wages, national differences have to be taken into account when devising policies.

Taxes should be prioritised in higher-income northern European countries with capital-intensive agricultural sectors such as Denmark or The Netherlands. Here, a tax-based approach targeting FLW in the Distribution & Retail and Consumption stages would be more effective in mitigating negative spillover effects, limiting the increase in agricultural production, linked to high use of fertiliser and GHG emissions. Moreover, the imposition of taxes in higher-income countries where consumers are more flexible to accommodate price changes, could help reduce spillover effects into non-food demand sectors, limiting the rise in non-food demand and related GHG emissions.

In high-labour intensive agricultural countries in southern Europe such as Italy or Spain, FLW reductions could boost labour demand and agricultural wages, indicating that policies should emphasise voluntary FLW reductions, because such measures are likely to have positive socio-economic impacts by driving production and job creation particularly in horticultural sectors. However, introducing parallel modest tax-based incentives could provide a balanced approach, encouraging higher producer efficiency without imposing high additional costs.

Finally, in countries where production primarily involves animal-based products, a blended approach combining voluntary measures with moderate tax-based interventions is recommended. Targeting plant-based commodities, which dominate FLW in these regions, could increase food security while simultaneously benefitting unskilled wages. However, to further fill the wage gap between skilled and unskilled workers, support for skill development in agricultural innovation could help increase wages, further driving unskilled workers into emerging sustainable practices.

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8. Annex I: Model aggregation

Figure S1. Regional aggregation.

Table S1. Macro sectoral aggregation sets.

Name	description	Components
LVST	Livestock	othctl, cattle, pigpls, pltry, milk
ANI2	Livestock using land	othctl, cattle, milk, wol
AGRI	Agriculture	pdr, wht, grain, veg, fruit, nuts, roots, pulses, oils, sug, oagr, crops, othctl, cattle, pigpls, pltry, milk, wol
SERV	Services	gas_dist, ser, foodserv, trans, edu, ros, dwe
INDS	Industry	oagr, wol, frs, plan, coa, oil, gas, oxt, cvol, oilcake, mola, fishm, texplus, wood, ppp, p_c, biog, biod, ddgs, bf2nd, respel, chm, bph, rpp, bioch, bioph, biopl, fert_n, fert_p, fert_k, manu, nmm, omf, ely, ely_c, ely_g, ely_n, ely_h, ely_w, bioe, heat, bioh, r_pdr, r_gro, r_osd, r_frs, WCR, WCG, WCGP, comp, incin, landf, recy, pagl, biom, wely, Bgas, Lfgas, fdctl, fdpig, fdplt, fdfsh, mnbctl, mnctl, mnoap, mnpltry, mnrnk
FOOD	Food commodities	pdr, wht, grain, veg, fruit, nuts, roots, pulses, oils, sug, crops, othctl, cattle, pigpls, pltry, milk, wfish, aqcltr, othcmt, bfmt, othmt, pulmt, vol, dairy, pcr, sugar, ofd, fishp, b_t, Swd
PRAG	Primary agri food	pdr, wht, grain, veg, fruit, nuts, roots, pulses, oils, sug, crops, othctl, cattle, pigpls, pltry, milk, wfish, aqcltr, Swd
PRFD	Processed food	othcmt, bfmt, othmt, pulmt, vol, dairy, pcr, sugar, ofd, fishp, b_t
FDSV	Food services	foodserv, ros
NONF	Non food commodities	oagr, wol, frs, plan, coa, oil, gas, oxt, cvol, oilcake, mola, fishm, texplus, wood, ppp, p_c, biog, biod, ddgs, bf2nd, respel, chm, bph, rpp, bioch, bioph, biopl, fert_n, fert_p, fert_k, manu, nmm, omf, ely, ely_c, ely_g, ely_n, ely_h, ely_w, bioe, heat, bioh, gas_dist, ser, trans, r_pdr, r_gro, r_osd, r_frs, pagl, biom, wely, edu, dwe, Bgas, Lfgas, fdctl, fdpig, fdplt, fdfsh, mnbctl, mnctl, mnoap, mnpltry, mnrnk
WASTE	Waste-related services	WCR, WCG, WCGP, comp, incin, landf, recy

Table S2. Agricultural commodity aggregation in figures.

MAGNET Commodity	Description	Macro category in figures
grain	Cereal grains nec	Cereals & grains
pcr	Processed rice	
pdr	Paddy and processed rice	
wht	Wheat	
dairy	Dairy products	Dairy
milk	Milk	
aqcltr	Aquaculture	Fish
fishp	Processed fish	
wfish	Wild Fish	

fruit	Fruit	
nuts	Nuts	
pulses	Pulses	Horticulture
roots	Roots and tubers	
veg	Vegetables	
bfmt	Beef meat	
othcmt	Other cattle meat	
othctl	Other cattle	
othmt	Other meat	Meat
pigpls	Pig Poultry	
pltry	Poultry	
pulmt	poultry meat	
oils	Oil seeds	
vol	Vegetable oils and fats	Oil seeds
sug	Sugar cane, sugar beet	
sugar	Sugar and molasses	Sugar beet/cane